

MASTER'S PROGRAMME PHILOSOPHY OF RELIGION

Perfect Being Theology and Eternal Conscious
Torment: Are They Compatible?

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Abstract

Are God and hell, as traditionally conceived, compatible or mutually exclusive ideas? Can a just and loving God consign people to unending punishment? This paper examines and defends the claim that Anselmian Perfect Being Theology (PBT)—which defines God as the greatest possible being—and the doctrine of Eternal Conscious Torment (ECT)—understood as a retributive and everlasting punishment inflicted upon unrepentant sinners—are not only compatible but necessarily interconnected. Thus, while ECT *appears* to conflict with the notion of a loving and just God, in this paper I argue that such punishment is a necessary consequence of divine perfection, reconciling God’s justice with His love.

With this end in mind, I begin by introducing the research topic, highlighting its relevance, detailing my methodology, and defining key terms. Then, I present the relevant theological and philosophical data, examining biblical and philosophical foundations concerning God’s nature and the nature of hell, as well as the theoretical framework within which I will develop my argument for ECT. Next, I briefly outline the four main views on hell and examine their theological and philosophical strengths and weaknesses, ultimately demonstrating how the ECT model aligns consistently with both Scripture and PBT, while the alternative views fall short of doing so. Afterward, I engage with the most prominent objections to ECT—whether theological, logical, or moral—demonstrating their shortcomings in undermining the ECT view. Finally, I demonstrate the robustness of my position: I explain my own view, defend my main argument regarding PBT and ECT compatibility, address my concerns regarding the doxastic acceptance of alternative views on hell, and articulate my eschatological hope, both theologically and philosophically.

Keywords: God, Hell, Perfect Being Theology, Eternal Conscious Torment, Coherence of Theism, Libertarian Free Will, Love, Mercy, Goodness, Holiness, Justice, Retributive Justice, Sin, Offense, Punishment, Infinite, Everlasting, Heaven, Possible Worlds, Feasible Worlds.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
BWW	Being Worthy of Worship
CU	Christian Universalism (Restorationism)
ECT	Eternal Conscious Torment (Traditionalism)
EPT	Equal Punishment Thesis
FMA	Free Moral Agent
FW	Feasible World
GPB	Greatest Possible Being
IPT	Infinite Punishment Thesis
ISS	Issuantism (Choice Model / Natural Consequences View of Hell)
LFW	Libertarian Free Will
NT	New Testament
OT	Old Testament
PBT	Perfect Being Theology
PW	Possible World
QI	Qualitatively Infinite
RJ	Retributive Justice
RP	Retributive Punishment
TP	Terminal Punishment (Annihilationism / Conditionalism)

I. Introduction

A. Rationale

1. *Significance*

Apart from the problem of evil and suffering, one of the most significant objections to Christianity that theologians have had to grapple with throughout church history is the compatibility of divine omnibenevolence—which encompasses God’s perfect love and justice—with the doctrine of hell. Traditionally, hell has been understood as a retributive punishment (RP) inflicted by God upon sinners, consciously experienced in a place of torment and darkness for all eternity after the final judgment. This traditionalist view is called Eternal Conscious Torment (ECT).

Many have wondered how it can even be just and proportionate to inflict infinite punishment on finite beings as a consequence of a finite number of sins committed over a finite lifetime. While this punitive question is a philosophical problem in itself, adding to it the consideration that a Perfect, Good, All-Loving, All-Knowing, and Just Being would be the one responsible for inflicting such a (presumably unjust) punishment makes it an even greater problem. The former would be a problem of retributive justice within the philosophy of law; the latter would be a problem of theology and philosophy of religion, specifically within philosophical theology, concerning the coherence of theism. Furthermore, in recent years, an increasing number of Christian theologians, philosophers, and biblical scholars who advocate annihilationism, universalism, or issuantist (choice model) views of hell have challenged the traditionalist reading of key passages regarding ECT. This has led to renewed debate over its theological, logical, and moral defensibility.

This study is significant because it contributes to the ongoing discussion on the coherence of theism by defending ECT within the framework of Anselmian Perfect Being Theology (PBT). It aims to demonstrate that the doctrine of ECT is not only *the best explanation* of the biblical data concerning divine justice and deserved punishment but also—and even more importantly for the philosophy of religion—*the most theologically and philosophically coherent account* for these, considering the metaphysical and ethical consequences of sinning/offending the most perfect being. In fact, I will argue that the existence of the Greatest Possible Being (GPB) would entail the

existence of ECT punishment in any possible world (PW) where two conditions are met: (1) there are free moral agents, and (2) at least one free moral agent has Sinned¹.

2. *Motivations*

The motivation behind this work is philosophical, theological, and spiritual:

First, it is *philosophical* because it involves the search for truth through reflection and philosophical analysis on one of the most basic existential questions that any worldview, aiming to be socially relevant, must address: where do we go after death? This is the question of individual and collective eschatology.

Secondly, it is *theological* because it seeks the truth of the message of special revelation within the Judeo-Christian tradition through exegesis and a coherent interpretation of the biblical texts on the subject. The doctrine of hell is part of the study of biblical eschatology.

Finally, it is *spiritual* because it concerns the search for truth in the relational sense with the Supreme Being, through repentance toward God, faith in Jesus (see Acts 20:21; Mark 1:15), and subsequent obedience to the Gospel commands (see Luke 3:8; John 14:15; James 2:17, 21, 26) as a result of saving faith (which connects us with God, enabling us to know Him and grow in sanctification, becoming conformed to His image).

Thus, much depends on what we believe about what God's Word (i.e., the Bible, understood as the supreme authority in matters of faith and practice for the Christian) teaches regarding the last things (eschatology), the possible destinations of human beings, and whether these destinations are reversible or irreversible. Much of what we believe today will determine what we do tomorrow. For example, if I believe in ECT for those who do not come to Christ, it will influence how I proclaim the Gospel to those around me—how much, with what passion, with what urgency, and with what kind of exhortations—so that they turn from their sins to the God who loves them so much that He sent His Son to save them. Likewise, my eschatological views will shape my daily spiritual walk. My level of passion and effort to “die” spiritually to “self” (see Romans 6; Colossians 3:5ff; Galatians 5:16–17; Luke 9:23) and to allow Christ to live through me (ultimately, my sense of urgency to cooperate with the sanctifying grace of the Holy Spirit) will depend on whether I believe that “I’ll have a chance to repent later” or that “it is now or never, because what I do today can make a difference for the glory of God in this world.” Similarly, the

¹ Here, I refer to “Sin” in uppercase, as defined in section I.C, *Definitions*.

nonbeliever might think, “If ultimately I will be annihilated (or sanctified in hell), I can live my own way now.” However, the Bible warns humans that “There is a way that seems right to a man, but its end is the way to death” (Proverbs 14:12, *ESV*, 2016). Therefore, although an error in biblical interpretation does not *determine* how a person will live, it can serve as an additional instrument of deception—or even self-deception—on the path to the afterlife, fostering false hopes that may lead to spiritually *deadly* eschatological consequences and, thus, to an unexpected final state or destiny.

3. Study and Research Backgrounds

In an earlier master’s thesis², I explored the compatibility between divine omniscience and human freedom, analyzing this debate through William Lane Craig’s work in philosophical theology. Thus, the inquiry into the coherence of theism not only became very familiar to me but also it came to be the primary focus of my philosophical interest and research. One of the possible applications of Molinism³ to controversial or difficult theological conundrums that I had briefly examined in that paper was how Molinism addresses the problem of an inhabited hell.

For the reasons stated above and due to the background mentioned here, among all possible topics, the issue of an inhabited hell in its traditional version (ECT) seemed to me both the most urgent and the most fascinating to address. Thus, having already examined the attribute of divine omniscience in my previous work, I now turn to the doctrine of hell and its compatibility with the attribute of divine goodness, which encompasses both divine love and divine justice. In doing so, not only will I consider the arguments of William L. Craig—one of the most prominent proponents of ECT in contemporary analytic philosophical theology—but also, I will engage with the views, defenses, and objections presented by other key scholars. Among philosophers, these include Oliver D. Crisp, Jerry L. Walls, Richard Swinburne, Ramon Baker, T. Parker Haratine and Kevin Smith, as well as critics like Thomas Talbott, Ryan T. Mullins, Theodore Sider, and Ray Bradely. From a theological perspective, I will consider contributions from Denny Burk, Robert A.

² Gamgebeli-Doroshenko, V. (2017). *La omnisciencia divina en la teología filosófica de William Lane Craig* [Divine Omniscience in the Philosophical Theology of William Lane Craig] [Master’s Thesis, Universidad Complutense de Madrid]. <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.14352/19902>

³ The philosophical-theological view that God possesses *middle knowledge* which is the knowledge of the counterfactuals of libertarian freedom in a manner logically prior to His decree to create the actual world.

Peterson, and James R. White, alongside objections raised by Edward W. Fudge, John G. Stackhouse, and Robin A. Parry, among others.

This study, therefore, is part of a broader debate on the coherence of theism, as it seeks to reconcile divine attributes within the PBT framework by examining their compatibility with the traditional ECT view of hell.

As Romerales (1994) observed, the way we interpret every attribute of God will carry certain costs or theological implications:

The problem of the nature of God is one of the most complex and widely discussed topics in contemporary scholarship. While the notion of God as the perfect being—that is, as an eternal, omnipresent spirit, free, creator of the universe, omnipotent, omniscient, perfectly good, the source of moral obligation, necessarily existent (aseity), and worthy of worship—may be coherent, or at least not demonstrably incoherent, each of these attributes individually raises its own set of questions.

Moreover, each attribute can be conceived in more than one way while maintaining coherence, and the interpretation we adopt for each will have implications for the others as well as for the resulting form of theism or theology. (p. 566)

This is why addressing this study properly is of considerable importance and why I have decided to undertake an investigation into this profoundly serious and sensitive issue. There is much at stake here.

B. Methodology

Being this study part of the coherence of theism philosophical inquiry, I follow the two guiding principles employed for this endeavor.

As Moreland and Craig (2017) indicate:

Two controls have tended to guide this inquiry into the divine nature: Scripture and perfect being theology. For thinkers in the Judeo-Christian tradition, God's self-revelation in Scripture is obviously paramount in understanding what God is like. In addition, the Anselmian conception of God as the greatest conceivable being or most perfect being—perfect being theology—has guided philosophical speculation on the raw data of Scripture,

so that God's biblical attributes are to be conceived in ways that would serve to exalt God's greatness. Since the concept of God is underdetermined by the biblical data and since what constitutes a "great-making" property is to some degree debatable, philosophers working within the Judeo-Christian tradition enjoy considerable latitude in formulating a philosophically coherent and biblically faithful doctrine of God. (chapter 27)

1. Framework

First of all, this study operates within the Judeo-Christian scriptural framework, treating the Bible as the foundational source of theological authority. Regarding the list of authoritative sacred books, I use the Jewish canon, equivalent to 39 books in the Christian Old Testament (OT), and the general Christian New Testament (NT) canon consisting of 27 books.

Secondly, as a hermeneutic method, I will be employing the *grammatical-historical method* of interpretation. Within the framework of the Protestant tradition, I start from the principle of the *perspicuity of Scripture* and interpret the texts following the principle of the *analogy of faith*. The theologians cited in support of my argument adhere to the same theological framework.

Thirdly, as for the philosophical analysis, this work is conducted under the PBT framework. Specifically, I subscribe to what is known as "neoclassical theism," as I maintain that attributes such as divine simplicity, immutability, and impassibility neither accurately represent the God of the Bible nor are they necessarily great-making properties within PBT. Hence, in my paper, I do not attempt to reconcile this form of theism with the doctrine of ECT.

Fourthly, my approach is rooted in philosophical theology, employing analytic philosophy of religion to assess the rationality of both PBT and ECT from logical, metaphysical, and ethical perspectives.

Fifthly, a key aspect of my approach to addressing objections to ECT and its compatibility with PBT is the assumption that both humans and angelic beings possess libertarian freedom. Consequently, to explain why there is ultimately a hell, I adopt a theological-philosophical framework classified as Arminian⁴ within these debates. Regarding theories of divine providence—and the rationale behind God's decision to create this world rather than any other possible world—I uphold a Craigian Molinism.

⁴ This view stands in contrast to the determinism characteristic of Augustinian-Calvinist theology, which rejects libertarian free will—an essential element in Arminianism.

Sixthly, regarding my position on the problem of religious diversity in the world, I hold to *Christian particularism*—“the view that only some, but not all, human beings will partake of God’s salvation” (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34). From this perspective, I identify theologically more with what Craig calls *Christian restrictivism*, although I recognize the possibility of *Christian accessibilism*, and I maintain a *Christian exclusivism*, although I recognize the possibility of a narrow *Christian inclusivism*⁵ (see Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34).

Finally, likewise, I adopt a Craigian penal substitution view of the atonement (see Craig, 2018). Since this study focuses on hell rather than atonement, I do not argue for penal substitution but instead assume it as both exegetically sound and philosophically coherent.

2. Structure

In section (II), I examine the theological and philosophical data and background information needed to properly understand the subsequent discussion of God’s nature and hell. This involves a systematic examination of biblical passages most frequently cited in favor of ECT, along with philosophical reasoning concerning divine attributes, especially justice and love.

Afterward, (III) I briefly outline the four main views on hell and examine their theological and philosophical strengths and weaknesses, ultimately demonstrating how the ECT model aligns consistently with both Scripture and PBT, while the alternative views fall short of doing so.

Next, (IV) I systematically engage with the most powerful objections to ECT posed by contemporary theologians and philosophers—whether theological, logical, or moral—showing how they fail to undermine the traditionalist viewpoint.

Finally, (V) I present my own view and defense, arguing for the compatibility of PBT and ECT. I close the section by addressing my concerns regarding the doxastic acceptance of alternative views on hell and articulating my eschatological hope, both theologically and philosophically.

With this approach I will not only argue for the compatibility between PBT and ECT but also defend the claim that such punishment is the necessary consequence of *Sin* when committed against God, the most perfect being.

⁵ I examine these and other concepts in the section V.A.

C. Definitions

These are the definitions of the main terms used throughout this paper, reflecting the view that I hold and will be defending. Other positions relevant to the debate will be discussed further in this paper.

- **God:** The Perfect Being, defined as such by virtue of possessing all the great-making properties—attributes and characteristics that make Him a Being Worthy of Worship (BWW). In other words, God is the Greatest Possible Being⁶ (GPB).

- **Perfect Being Theology (PBT):** The Anselmian conception of God as the GPB, which, along with Scripture, is one of the *two controls* that tended to guide the philosophical inquiry into divine nature (Moreland & Craig, 2017).

- **Hell:** The place or state where the wicked—those who reject God and His every effort to save them—will, after their eschatological bodily resurrection, experience a sempiternal, final, and irreversible separation from God, His people, and His blessings, as a result of *Sin*⁷ (and of sins, as its fruit). Within the framework of Christian theology, hell is a just retributive punishment (RP), consisting in sinners being separated from God and deprived of all the benefits that, by His grace (i.e., unmerited favor), they receive daily on earth. As a result, they suffer endless conscious torment. The punishment may arise from:

- a. Having committed the Sin of rejecting God’s general revelation (manifested in nature and conscience), using their Libertarian Free Will (LFW), thereby failing to respond to the light available to them during this life.

- b. Having committed the Sin of rejecting the Gospel message of Jesus Christ after having committed at least one sin in this life, using their LFW.

- c. Other combinations of levels of understanding/awareness of (a) and (b), which entail varying degrees of moral responsibility and, consequently, varying degrees of everlasting punishment⁸.

⁶ Also called *the Greatest Conceivable Being* (Craig), *the Maximally Great Being* (Plantinga), *a Being than which Nothing Greater can be Conceived* (Anselm) and *the Most Perfect Being* (Maimonides). In other words, a *Maximally Excellent Being* or *the Most Virtuous Being Possible*.

⁷ See below for the definition of *sin*, along with the distinctions made between *Sin* and *sin(s)*.

⁸ In order to keep the definition concise, I do not address the case of the punishment of rebellious or fallen angels, for whom redemption seems impossible given the seriousness of their sin considering their epistemic closeness to God in heaven and given the apparently irreversible nature of decisions made in eternity. In sum, their rebellion involved preferring secondary goods over the Supreme Good (God). According to the Bible, hell was prepared “for the devil

- **Eternal Conscious Torment (ECT):** The theological/philosophical view of hell that, in the afterlife, sinners will experience endless conscious suffering in hell as retributive punishment (RP) for the sins they have freely committed (using LFW) during their lifetime.

- **Libertarian Free Will (LFW):** The metaphysical ability of rational beings to make genuine choices, i.e., to do x or to refrain from doing x . In Moreland & Craig's (2017, chapter 13) words, "I can literally choose to act or refrain from choosing to act. No circumstances exist that are sufficient to determine my choice. My choice is up to me. I act as an agent who is the ultimate originator of my own actions."⁹ Thus, we could say that a person P is a Free Moral Agent (FMA) *if and only if* P possesses LFW.

- **Goodness:** The supreme moral value and virtue defined by God's moral nature (or character). It can be considered an essential moral attribute of God. God is the ontological foundation of this and all other objective moral values (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 26). Thus, as Moreland & Craig, (2017, chapter 28) point out, "God is essentially compassionate, fair, kind, impartial, and so forth, and his commandments are reflections of his own character". In fact, the systematic theologian, Millard Erickson (2013, chapter 12) identifies the moral attributes encompassed within God's goodness in Christian theology:

- (1) Moral purity (holiness, righteousness, justice)
- (2) Integrity (genuineness, veracity, faithfulness)
- (3) Love (benevolence, grace, and mercy)

Consequently, as for humans—and for any FMA—*being* morally good and *acting* in a morally good way means *reflecting* God's moral character (or nature) which "is expressed in relation to us in the form of divine commands, which constitute our moral duties or obligations" (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 26).

- **Love:** An essential attribute of God characterized by selfless, disinterested, and altruistic giving to others for their sake. In Christian theology, "God is love" (see 1 John 4:7–10). For created

and his angels" (Matthew 25:41, *ESV*, 2016)—not for human beings. Nevertheless, humans will also go to hell if they follow the pattern of conduct of those fallen celestial beings.

⁹ For the sake of clarity, I include the rest of Moreland's consideration about the nature of LFW: "Moreover, my reasons for acting do not partially or fully cause my actions; I myself bring about my actions. Rather, my reasons are the teleological goals or purposes for the sake of which I act. If I get a drink because I am thirsty, the desire to satisfy my thirst is the end for the sake of which I myself act freely. I raise my arm *in order to* vote" (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 13).

FMA, love implies a determination to act (live, behave, or work) for the good of others, motivated by love for God (desiring to glorify Him and to do what is pleasing in His sight). Thus, loving others necessarily implies acting for their good, out of love for God. Analogically, loving God necessarily implies acting for His good (glory, pleasure), out of love for Him (i.e., out of worship).

Moreover, according to the NT, God's love is (1) universal, (2) impartial, and (3) unconditional (Craig, n.d.-a). This aligns perfectly with the PBT requirement of *moral perfection* in God.

- **Mercy:** A derivative (or secondary) attribute of God that flows from His primary attribute of love and is characterized by compassion and a “tenderness of heart toward the needy” (Erickson, 2013, chapter 12). In the context of just judgment, God's mercy means that He withholds the punishment sinners rightfully deserve for their wrongdoing. Instead, He demonstrates patience and care, granting new opportunities to those guilty of breaking His commandments. Mercy ends where justice begins. When the time comes for God to judge an individual or a group—either because they have exceeded the limits of what His patience deems tolerable during their earthly life or because He sovereignly chooses to judge them at a specific moment in history—justice takes over. Nevertheless, in many cases, mercy continues to be present during the sinners' earthly life. However, this will no longer be the case at the final judgment, when the wicked “will suffer the punishment of eternal destruction, away from the presence of the Lord and from the glory of his might” (2 Thessalonians 1:9, *ESV*, 2016).

- **Grace:** An attribute or expression of God's love that—in view of humanity's sin, guilt, and state of condemnation—consists of treating people according to their needs rather than their merits, worthiness, or deserts. In other words, it is God's unearned favor and kindness, freely given based on His goodness and love, not on human merit or worthiness (Erickson, 2013). Grace is exemplified in salvation (i.e., deliverance from sin and its consequences), which is a gift of God through faith, apart from works, to anyone who believes (i.e., puts their trust) in Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior (see Ephesians 2:8–9).

- **Holiness:** An essential attribute of God that, within Christian theology, can, depending on the context, refer either to (1) God's *transcendence*—a metaphysical quality of ontological distinctness, otherness or uniqueness (see Exodus 15:11; 1 Samuel 2:2; Isaiah 6:1–4; 57:15)—or to (2) God's *moral purity*—His absolute intolerance of, and incompatibility with, moral deviation

(see Job 34:12; Habakkuk 1:13; James 1:13)¹⁰, the privation of good, or moral imperfection, understood in light of His general attribute of goodness. In his detailed study on this subject, Murphy (2021, chapters 2-3) shows how these aspects combine in what he calls God’s *primary holiness*—His perfect nature, which, he observes, evokes an appropriate ‘dual response’: it both *attracts (fascinans)*, creating desire or longing for Him, and *repels (tremendum)*, revealing human unworthiness.

- **Justice:** An essential moral attribute of God, closely related to His goodness, characterized by righteousness, fairness, and equity. This attribute is manifested in creation through His truth-grounded, wise, and impartial judgments in this life, as well as through the rewards and penalties assigned to each FMA in the afterlife. As the ATS Bible Dictionary (*Justice*, n.d.) states, justice is the attribute of God “which makes his nature and his ways the perfect embodiment of equity, and constitutes him the model and the guardian of equity throughout the universe.” It further adds, “The justice of God could not leave the world without laws, and cannot fail to vindicate them by executing their penalties.” In the biblical context, justice also refers to a legal standing before God, signifying a righteousness that is imputed or transferred to the “account” of repentant sinners who have placed their trust (faith) in Jesus Christ as their Redeemer (see 2 Corinthians 5:21; Romans 4:3; 5:1).

- **Retributive Justice (RJ):** A theory of justice and a legal concept that involves responding to criminal behavior by punishing offenders and compensating victims, with the punishment’s severity proportionate to the crime’s seriousness (Meyer, 2025). Theologically, it is part of God’s nature, meaning that God will punish the guilty. He is a *positive retributivist* who ensures that the guilty receive their just deserts and He is a *negative retributivist* only qualifiedly (see Craig, 2018b, p. 71). According to the Bible, God “will by no means clear the guilty” (Exodus, 34:7, *ESV*, 2016). RP is a good because it is the way God restores justice in the universe, ensuring that happiness corresponds to righteousness (Haratine & Smith, 2023). In Craig’s (2025) words: “retributivism as a theory of justice is the positive thesis that punishment of the guilty is an intrinsic good because the guilty deserve it” (p. 454).

¹⁰ The biblical references for “Holiness” are taken from Erickson (2013, chapter 12).

- **Sin:** A deliberate violation of God’s purpose by a FMA, which can occur through commission or omission, in motivation, thought, word, or deed. Within the framework of Biblical theology, by *sin* can be meant, at least¹¹, two different ideas:

(1) What I call *Sin* (with an uppercase “S”) refers to the rejection of God as Lord over a person’s life through

(a) the desire for independence from God, seeking autonomy in the moral sphere instead of submission to His will, or

(b) the rejection of the Gospel of Jesus Christ, whereby a person refuses to place their trust in Him for salvation from the penalty of Sin and its everlasting consequences.

(2) What I call *sin(s)* (with a lowercase “s”) refers to any other transgression of God’s law or violation of His purpose that stems from (1). These derived kinds of sins include acts such as lying, stealing, blaspheming, fornicating, envying, insulting, hating, and so on. These are the fruit (result) of the abovementioned spiritual alienation, called (spiritual) *death* in the Bible (see Genesis 2:17; Ephesians 2:1).

- **Offense:** A wrongdoing against someone; a transgression, infraction, insult, affront, or fault. In the context of this discussion, the term refers to morally wounding God’s dignity by violating the order He established, thereby incurring a moral transgression. The concept is used similarly to the notion of *sin*.

- **Punishment:** “A penalty assigned to or imposed for an offense or fault” (*Punishment - WordReference.com Dictionary of English*, 2025). The “infliction of some kind of pain or loss upon a person for a misdeed (i.e., the transgression of a law or command)” (Allott et al., 2024). A plausible definition of punishment, drawn from debates in the philosophy of law¹², is: *harsh*

¹¹ The Bible also refers to the fallen nature as “sin” or “sinful,” which, being devoid of the life of God in the human spirit, becomes a nature enslaved to the passions and desires that arise from humanity’s alienation from God. The apostle Paul calls this principle of rebellion against God’s order—His law (Romans 7:7) and His Spirit (Romans 8:5–8)—“the flesh.” He thus speaks of “sin dwelling in me” as an enslaving principle (Romans 7:17, 20) and of “the desires of the flesh” as those that arise from this fallen nature (Romans 13:14; Galatians 5:24; Ephesians 2:3) which lead people to live “according to the flesh” (Romans 8:5). Accordingly, God’s promise is to free humans from (1) the *guilt* of sin through justification by faith, (2) the *power* of sin through sanctification throughout the Christian life, and (3) the *presence* of sin through glorification—i.e., the eschatological resurrection of the body, which confers immortality on believers in Christ.

¹² This definition is mainly based on “Alec Walen’s characterization of some of the necessary conditions of punishment in a standard philosophical encyclopedia” (Craig, 2018b, p. 55).

treatment intentionally imposed as a cost, hardship, or loss of benefit (by a recognized authority) in response to a wrongful act or omission, often (though not necessarily) expressing condemnation or censure. It must be deliberate, not accidental, and directly tied to the wrongdoing. (Craig, 2018b)

As the *Topical Bible (Punishment, n.d.)* Encyclopedia indicates:

Punishment in the biblical context refers to the consequences or penalties imposed for sin or disobedience to God's laws. It is both a divine and human response to wrongdoing, serving as a means of justice, correction, and deterrence. The Bible presents punishment as an expression of God's holiness and righteousness, ensuring that sin does not go unaddressed.

- **Retribution:** Deserved payment, recompense, or vengeance.
- **Everlasting:** Endless, eternal (sempiternal), never-ending, perpetual, permanent, enduring forever, infinite in duration or experience, and uninterrupted in its continuity. As for God, the most appropriate word is 'eternal', regardless of whether He is conceived as *timeless* or *omnitemporal*. As for hell, I use 'sempiternal' or 'everlasting' to denote an event, such as punishment, that has a temporal beginning but no end. Hell is temporally infinite *a parte post*—i.e., it has endless future duration after a temporal origin.
- **Heaven:** The abode of God and the future eternal dwelling place of believers (Erickson, 2013). More specifically, it is the place or state where the righteous—those who had a personal relationship with God by trusting in His grace and mercy—will, after their eschatological bodily resurrection, experience sempiternal bliss in the presence of God, united with His people, and enjoying His blessings forever. Within the framework of Christian theology, heaven is an unmerited blessing, consisting in the redeemed being united with God and enjoying all the benefits that flow from His presence, love, and glory. As a result, they experience endless joy, peace, and fulfillment¹³. The blessing may arise from:
 - a. Having responded to God's general revelation (in nature and conscience) through faith and trust in the Self-revealed Creator, during this life, using their LFW (and as a result, seeking truth and righteousness during their life).

¹³ For a fuller description, heaven represents a state of blessedness, sinlessness, joy, and peace, characterized by the presence of God, perfect knowledge, the removal of all evils, and immense glory (Erickson, 2013).

b. Having accepted the Gospel message of Jesus Christ and receiving forgiveness for their sins, using their LFW to place their faith in Christ.

c. Other combinations of levels of understanding/awareness of (a) and (b), which entail varying degrees of moral responsibility and, consequently, varying degrees of eternal reward in God's presence.

- **Possible World (PW):** As Moreland and Craig (2017, chapter 2) indicate, it is “a way the world might be ... a maximal description of reality” where “nothing is left out. It may be thought of as ... an enormous conjunction composed of every statement or its contradictory.” Here I mean *strict logical possibility*.

- **Feasible World (FW):** A (sort of) possible world that is “actualizable”, i.e., a maximal state of affairs *metaphysically* “capable of being actual”. As Moreland and Craig (2017, chapter 2) point out, the statements that compose a possible world “must be compossible, that is, able ... to be true together, otherwise they would not constitute a possible world.” For a FW one or both conditions may be required: (1) The PW is *broadly logically possible*, or also (2) the PW is *metaphysically possible*¹⁴.

II. Data and Framework

In this section, I discuss the essential background information required for a proper understanding of the debate concerning God and hell, emphasizing the crucial role of ECT in making sense of both doctrines.

A. Theological Background: What is the Biblical Data?

1. Concerning God

a. Concept and Attributes. God is the Supreme Being, the creator and sustainer of all things, both visible and invisible, who, according to the Judeo-Christian Scriptures, is both *infinite* (see, e.g., Job 11:7–9) and personal (see, e.g., Exodus 34:7). God possesses the so-called *incommunicable attributes*, such as omnipotence, omniscience, omnipresence, eternity,

¹⁴ For a more detailed discussion, see Moreland and Craig, 2017 (chapter 2, 2.1.3).

immutability, incorporeality, and aseity, as well as *communicable attributes*, such as goodness¹⁵, holiness, justice, and love¹⁶.

Throughout Judeo-Christian sacred history, the only true God, whose name is Yahweh, has revealed Himself as existing in three divine persons—distinct in personhood yet equal in nature and attributes, i.e., the Father, the Son (the Word or *Logos*) and the Holy Spirit¹⁷. From eternity, God decrees to create and redeem humanity so that they may partake in eternal communion with Him (Matthew 25:34; Revelation 13:8). This love relationship of glory, bliss and joy constitutes the *summum bonum* of human existence and its ultimate purpose (Psalm 16:2, 11; 73:25).

b. Attributes and Texts. The following are key biblical references¹⁸ supporting the divine attributes most relevant to the discussion in this paper.

1) **Omnipotence:** [Genesis 17:1; 18:14; Revelation 19:6; Romans 4:17; Jeremiah 32:17; 26-27; Job 42:1-2; Mark 14:36; Matthew 19:26.](#)

2) **Omniscience:** [Psalm 139:1-6; 139:14b-16; 44:21; 147:5; Job 34:21-22; Proverbs 15:3; Matthew 10:29-30; 1 Chronicles 28:9; Isaiah 41:21-24; 46:9b-10; 1 Samuel 23:1-13; Romans 11:33-36.](#)

3) **Omnipresence:** [Psalm 139:7-12; Jeremiah 23:23-24; 1 Kings 8:27; Acts 17:24, 28a.](#)

4) **Eternity:** [Psalm 102:11-12; 25-27; 90:2, 5-6; Job 36:26; Isaiah 41:4.](#)

5) **Immutability** (unchangeability): [Psalm 102:25-27; Malachi 3:6; James 1:17; Psalm 119:89-90; Hebrews 6:17-18; Psalm 33:11.](#)

6) **Holiness**¹⁹: [Isaiah 6:3; Habakkuk 1:13; 1 Peter 1:16-17; Revelation 4:8.](#)

7) **Justice:** [Deuteronomy 32:4; Psalm 7:11; 119:137; 145:17; Nahum 1:2-3; Romans 12:19; 1 John 3:7.](#)

¹⁵ As Craig (2025) notes, in the OT biblical context, the Hebrew word translated as ‘goodness’ has more to do with “beneficence or generosity” than with God’s moral goodness (p. 449). Indeed, as John Feinberg (2006, *cited in Doctrine of God [Part 18]*, 2023) points out, “biblical writers capture that idea by referring to his righteousness and holiness” (p. 366). That is why to construct an adequate understanding of God’s moral goodness from Scripture, analysis of the use of such terms is required. Such an analysis would indicate that ‘righteousness’ covers the attributes of both God’s love and justice, while the analysis of ‘holiness’—apart from its sense of ‘metaphysically transcendent’—covers God’s moral purity: “God as a standard of righteousness” and as “absolutely holy” (*Doctrine of God [Part 18]*, 2023). For further discussion, see Craig’s *Doctrine of God [Part 18]* (2023).

¹⁶ For further discussion about divine attributes, see Erickson (2013, part 3) and Craig’s *Doctrine of God | Reasonable Faith* (n.d.).

¹⁷ For a robust Craigian defense of the ‘biblical doctrine of the Trinity’, see *Doctrine of Trinity (Part 2)* (2023) and his main essay *Tri-Personal Monotheism* in McIntosh (2024).

¹⁸ The most of the references are selected from the relevant sections of *Doctrine of God | Reasonable Faith* (n.d.).

¹⁹ Here I avoid *goodness*, as this characteristic of God encompasses the three key moral attributes—holiness, justice, and love—as previously discussed in section I.C., *Definitions*.

8) **Love:** [1 John 4:7-12](#); [Deuteronomy 7:7-8](#); [Ephesians 2:4-5](#); [Titus 3:3-5](#); [Jeremiah 31:3](#); [John 3:16](#); [Romans 5:8](#).

c. Heavenly States. To be in heaven or paradise—in the so-called *intermediate state* that follows immediately after death—means “gain ... to depart and be with Christ, for that is far better” (Philippians 1:21, 23, *ESV*, 2016) than remaining on earth; it implies being “be away from the body and at home with the Lord” (2 Corinthians 5:8, *ESV*, 2016). The presence of God, according to Scripture, is associated with fullness of joy, peace, and blessing.

On the other hand, to be in the *eschatological* heaven—i.e., life in the new creation—means living in the very presence of God (1 Thessalonians 4:17), in everlasting friendship and communion with Him (Revelation 21:3), where “death shall be no more, neither shall there be mourning, nor crying, nor pain anymore” (Revelation 21:4, *ESV*, 2016). It is the world of justice, joy, peace, and fulfillment for which God created human beings from the beginning (Mathew 25:34; 5:1–12).

2. Concerning Hell

a. Concept and Characteristics. *Hell* is a general term for the state of postmortem punishment that the damned will experience. The relevant concept for this study is that of *Gehenna*, which, in the New Testament, is also referred to by interchangeable terms such as “unquenchable fire,” “furnace of fire,” “lake of fire and sulfur,” and similar expressions. Although this state or place of punishment is sempiternal, not everyone who goes there will suffer in the same way. In fact, the NT repeatedly teaches that there will be *degrees of punishment*, proportional to the light each one received. This is precisely the case because hell is a condition of just retribution: since God is just, RP does not fall with the same degree or intensity upon all the damned.

b. Relevant Vocabulary. There are several terms associated with the concept of hell that should not be confused:

1) ***Gehenna*:** the key term for what is properly called hell in the NT. As Sprinkle (2016) points out, the word is used twelve times in it and “is derived from the OT prophetic passages that talk about God’s future judgment of the wicked in the Valley of Hinnom, or Gehenna (Jer. 7:29–34; 19:6–9; 32:55)” (p. 11). He also notes that “Jews around the time of Jesus coined the term ... as the place where the wicked would be punished” (p. 11).

2) **Hades**: the place of torment in the *intermediate state* (Luke 16:19–31), where the souls of the wicked experience a disembodied, hellish state that lasts until the eschatological Judgment Day (Revelation 20:14). *Sheol* is the Hebrew equivalent of Hades, though in the OT it designates the place of both the righteous and the wicked.

3) **Abyss**: the temporary pre-eschatological prison of Satan and his demons (Revelation 9:1–2; 20:1–3; Luke 8:13).

4) **Tartarus**: the permanent prison for fallen angels, who are kept for the divine eschatological judgment in pits or chains of gloomy darkness (2 Peter 2:4).

c. Main Texts. [Isaiah 66:22-24](#); [Daniel 12:2-3](#); [Mathew 18:6-9](#); [25:31-46](#); [Mark 9:42-48](#); [2 Thessalonians 1:6-10](#); [Jude 7, 13](#); [Revelation 14:9](#)²⁰.

d. Hellish States. To be in hell or *Hades*—in the so-called *intermediate state* that follows immediately after death—means “being in torment”, conscious (aware of one’s surroundings and miserable state), “in anguish”, “in flame”, having one’s desires or needs unsatisfied, being separated from the people of God, without any possibility to escape, understanding of the horrors awaiting others who might end up in the same place and, lastly, being aware that the hellish state is avoidable through repentance during their lifetime, on earth (Luke 16:19–31, *ESV*, 2016).

On the other hand, to be in the *eschatological* hell or *Gehenna* means to “suffer the punishment of eternal destruction, away from the presence of the Lord and from the glory of his might” (2 Thessalonians 1:9). There, “those who are self-seeking [contentious] and do not obey the truth, but obey unrighteousness” (Romans 2:8), already with resurrected bodies, will experience the “second death,” i.e., being cast into the “outer darkness” (Matthew 8:12), into the “lake which burns with fire and sulfur” (Revelation 21:8), “where their worm does not die and the fire is not quenched” (Mark 9:48). In this place, they will endure the “wrath and fury” of God (Romans 2:8; Revelation 14:10a), the result of which will be “weeping and gnashing of teeth” (Luke 13:28), and “the smoke of their torment” will rise “forever and ever,” with “no rest, day or night” (Revelation 14:11). It is the place of curse, unfulfilled desire, mourning and weeping, tribulation and distress, perdition (ruination), and everlasting punishment—prepared by God for “the devil and his angels.” (Luke 6:25; Romans 2:9, 12; Matthew 25:41, *ESV*, 2016).

²⁰ The list is taken from Burk (2016, p. 21).

e. Degrees of Punishment. According to the Bible, not everyone who is in hell will suffer the same *degree of punishment*. Below, I present the rationale and the NT texts that support this doctrine.

1) **Rationale:** While the NT affirms that the wicked will face eternal punishment and that all people possess a general revelation of God in nature (Romans 1:18–20)²¹ and conscience (Romans 2:12, 14–15)²², it also clearly teaches that the severity of hellish punishment will be proportional to the light (degree of revelation, knowledge, or understanding) that the condemned had. In other words, *to whom much is given, much will be required*. Thus, every FMA that is in hell will experience a degree of punishment corresponding to the measure of light they had at the time of committing their sins. Their hellish torment will reflect the extent of the truth they disregarded during their lifetime. Regarding the reasons for such degrees, Martin and Zaspel (n.d.) indicate:

The infliction of punishment proportionately in degrees is an outworking of divine justice. Scripture repeatedly affirms that God will judge “in righteousness” (Acts 17:31) and that it is a function of God’s justice and glory to avenge every wrong (Rev. 16:1–7; 19:1–6). It is in the interests of divine justice that punishment will be given out according to the nature of the offence. (Martin & Zaspel, n.d.)

In fact, the Scripture insists that judgment will be “according to works” (Rom. 2:6) with “books opened” (Rev. 20:12) to weigh guilt and assign precise punishment. God judges deeds, words (Matt. 12:37), and even the thoughts and motives (Rom. 2:16), ensuring each sinner receives exactly what they deserve (Martin & Zaspel, n.d.).

As for the bases for determining the punishment degrees, Martin and Zaspel (n.d.) rightly point out that “Scripture sets forth at least three considerations:”

1. “The Extent to which a Person has Abandoned Himself to Sin:” Resisting God and persisting in doing one’s own will leads individuals to accumulate greater guilt, like storing up wrath for judgment (see Romans 2:5; Revelation 18:6–7).

2. “The Extent to which a Person by Example and Influence has Led Others to Sin:” False teachers, negligent parents, or those who obstruct the truth bear greater guilt and will face

²¹ This text is the Christian theological basis for cosmological and teleological arguments for theism.

²² That is, the moral or natural law, written in conscience. This text is the Christian theological basis for the moral argument for theism.

intensified punishment (see Matthew 18:5–7; 23:13). God’s omniscience allows Him to assess the full ripple effect of each person’s life influence, even across generations.

3. “The Extent to which Light and Privilege were Abused:” Greater knowledge (e.g., witnessing Christ’s miracles, hearing the gospel) brings greater accountability. E.g. Jesus declared that those who reject His gospel’s light (meaning the cities where He developed His earthly ministry), will face harsher judgment than the pagan cities of Sodom and Tyre (see Matthew 11:20–24). Similarly, Jesus taught that, in His eschatological second coming, “that servant who knew his master’s will but did not get ready or act according to his will, will receive a severe beating. But the one who did not know, and did what deserved a beating, will receive a light beating” (Luke 12:47–48a). (Martin & Zaspel, n.d.)

2) **Supporting Texts:** [Matthew 10:15](#); [Matthew 11:20-24](#); [Matthew 12:36-37](#); [Matthew 18:5-7](#); [Matthew 23:13](#); [Luke 12:42-48](#); [John 9:41](#); [John 15:22, 24](#); [John 19:11-12](#); [Romans 2:5](#); [Hebrews 10:28-29](#); [James 3:1-2](#); [2 Peter 2:20-22](#); [Revelation 20:12-13](#).

B. Philosophical Background: What is the Logic?

1. Behind God

a. Concept. God, as the only BWW²³, is the GPB. God’s perfect moral nature (or character) is the foundation of every objective moral value, and His divine commands constitute the source of every objective moral duty or obligation. Furthermore, the GPB must necessarily be one in being but plural in persons. This is because to love eternally seems to require an eternal object of love—which, in the case of God as the GPB, cannot be a contingent being created *ad hoc* for the purpose of love, as that would render Him less than the greatest conceivable being. Therefore, the beloved must be eternally inherent to His self-existent nature. This aligns with Christian theism: God is ontologically a being with three centers of self-consciousness. This implies that the persons constituting the nature of God exist in an eternal love relationship, lacking nothing. It also follows that creation must be an act of grace, not one of necessity. This demonstrates the coherence of the theistic account of a perfect personal being who created the universe and every FMA, so that they may enjoy a personal love relationship and fellowship with Him forever.

²³ See the *Definitions* section (I.C) or *Abbreviations* (p. 4).

b. Attributes. God, as the GPB, possesses all great-making properties—non-moral ones such as aseity (self-existence), necessary existence, eternality, and maximal power, knowledge, and presence, as well as moral ones such as perfect love, mercy, justice, and holiness—all to an infinite degree, thereby making Him a *qualitatively infinite being*.

In fact, it is *God's infinite goodness* that ultimately accounts for the existence of both heaven and hell²⁴.

c. Arguments. For a rational justification of PBT kind of theism and Judeo-Christianity in the context of this work, I consider that these three arguments are of utmost importance:

1) **The Ontological Argument:** Plantinga's (1974) *modal ontological argument*, a highly respected reformulation of the classical argument, employs modal logic (PW semantics). It moves from the possibility of a *maximally great being* to its actuality, i.e., it shows that if the existence of such a being is even possible, then it necessarily exists in all PWs. If sound, it is a strong *a priori* argument for theism, which, when combined with other theistic arguments, strengthens a cumulative case for the existence of God.

2) **The Moral Argument:** If sound, Craig's (2004) deductive version would establish the truth of theism by grounding objective moral values and duties in God. Baggett and Walls's (2016) abductive version would show that theism is probably true, i.e., that it best explains the existence of objective moral facts.

3) **The Historical Case for Jesus' Resurrection:** If sound, it confirms Jesus of Nazareth's divine identity and provides epistemic access to God's nature through Jesus' life and teachings (see, e.g., Craig, 2024a, 2024b; Habermas & Licona, 2004; Licona, 2010; Loke, 2021; Wright, 2003).

d. Heavenly states. If (a) God exists, if (b) FMAs have Sinned²⁵, and if (c) He has entered into their world to rescue them from their Sin, and its consequences²⁶, then (d) those FMAs who have met the God-given conditions for receiving the necessary legal pardon²⁷ can reasonably

²⁴ I elaborate on this below in section II.B.2 (pp. 24-27).

²⁵ Note the intentional use of "Sin" with a capital "S" when referring specifically to the concept as defined in section I.C., *Definitions*, which includes both senses (a) and (b) as stated therein (p. 15). Whether it involves the general rejection of God or, more specifically, the rejection of the Gospel of Jesus Christ, the result is a Sin of infinite gravity.

²⁶ The justification for the conditional (c) is discussed in section II.B.2 (p. 26).

²⁷ These conditions, in light of the Gospel, are *repentance* and *faith* in (or believing in) Jesus Christ (see Mark 1:14–15; Acts 20:21). *Repentance* involves turning away from living according to one's own will and surrendering the lordship of one's life to God (Acts 3:19; 20:21). *Faith* entails trusting that in Jesus as Savior (John 1:12–13; 6:47; 20:3), who accomplished, through His sacrificial death on the cross (Romans 3:25), what is sufficient for one's

expect to enter a sempiternal state in which they will enjoy the love of God and experience fullness (plenitude) and everlasting bliss in His presence—thereby fulfilling the ultimate and highest purpose for which they were created.

2. *Behind Hell*

a. Why Hell? Hell exists because both God and the Sin of FMAs exist. Its existence is contingent upon the actualization of moral evil by FMAs; if there were no FMAs, there would be no hell. The “fire” of hell is nothing other than the holy and just, retributive reaction of the One who is both the standard of morality and the moral arbiter of the universe—personally. That fire is also known in Christian theology as the “holy wrath of God”. That is, if such a maximally great God exists, He could not leave any manifestation of moral evil committed by FMAs unpunished—thereby remaining passive toward it. It is His *ontological obligation* (a moral obligation grounded in His own perfect nature) to do justice. Hence, every evil action freely committed by FMAs deserves to be proportionately punished, so that the divine order—which is good by virtue of coming from the Perfect Being—is restored.

b. Why ECT? Having examined the logic of PBT and of hell as RP inflicted upon unrighteous FMAs to restore justice and order in the universe, I shall now proceed to argue that ECT constitutes *the only* form of punishment for Sinners that coheres with the nature of the GPB.

My main thesis is that the existence of a GPB *entails* an ECT kind of punishment in any PW where, at least, two conditions are met:

- (a) FMAs exist
- (b) At least one FMA has Sinned

The following account²⁸ demonstrates both the *compatibility* and *necessary interconnection* between PBT and ECT:

The GPB is a BWW, and all FMAs were created to have a blissful love relationship with Him and are morally obligated to render to Him what He rightly deserves—i.e., the appropriate response of worship, expressed through wholehearted love²⁹ for Him ‘with all one’s being and

redemption (Romans 4:5)—and that, as confirmation of this redemptive act, God rose Jesus from the dead (Romans 10:9; Acts 17:31).

²⁸ This represents my view on the logic of heaven and hell: if a GPB exists and FMAs’ Sin is committed, then I find no reasonable alternative to ECT as the ultimate destiny of the wicked. My account of heaven and hell is a synthesis of Anselm’s *Cur Deus Homo* atonement theory and my own reflections grounded in PBT.

²⁹ For a better understanding of this concept, see *Love* in the *Definitions* section I.C. (pp. 12-13).

strength³⁰,’ and demonstrated through perfect obedience to His commands as the natural expression and outworking of that love.

If, however, FMAs Sin³¹—i.e., if they reject Him as Lord of their lives—they incur a kind of debt that, due to the ontological greatness of the GPB³²—i.e., His qualitative infinity (QI)—would be *metaphysically impossible* for them to repay.

The satisfaction³³ of this debt, due to the holiness and justice of the GPB—who must rectify any moral disorder caused by FMAs in His universe—would require a QI compensation rendered by each FMA to the GPB.

However, since such satisfaction is impossible for a Sinful and finite being to give, all FMAs would necessarily have to spend the rest of their existence suffering the consequences of their unfathomable injustice³⁴ (i.e., their Sin or disobedience).

If they ceased to exist—thus ending their conscious punishment—their infinitely serious (or grave) offense would remain everlastingly unpunished. Thus, a sempiternal unpaid debt would

³⁰ See the biblical *Greatest Commandment* (Deuteronomy 6:4–5; Mark 12:29–30) which represents the heart of the law (*Torah*).

³¹ I use the terms *disobedience*, *evil*, *Sin*, *rebellion*, *offense*, and *injustice* interchangeably in this context. The purpose of employing varied terminology, depending on the sentence, is to help the reader grasp the different nuances that an offense of such magnitude entails for the GPB.

³² The rationale here is that FMAs incur a qualitatively infinite debt because the offended party—the GPB—is a qualitatively infinite being. No contingent being can, metaphysically speaking, compensate Him by satisfying the demands of His justice.

³³ *Satisfaction*, *compensation*, and *debt payment* are related terms that, in some sentences, may even be used here almost interchangeably. One can *satisfy* the demands of God’s justice or a debt contracted with someone; one may *compensate* someone for damage caused; and one may *pay a debt* to an individual or an institution. A debt can be moral, economic, or religious—that is, involving the obligation to give something owed to someone.

³⁴ This justifies the transition from a qualitatively infinite RP (deserved by sinners) to a quantitatively infinite RP. The leap is warranted because, since the attribute of infinity is incommunicable, the only way to punish the guilty justly is by prolonging their RP endlessly—*ad infinitum*. Thus, once the punishment begins, there would be ECT—everlasting punishment. From the moment of judgment onward, the wicked would remain in a continual state of misery to satisfy the justice of the GPB and ensure order in His universe. By way of illustration of the justice involved in a transition from a qualitative offense to a satisfaction expressed in a temporally tensed state of punishment, suffice the example of when a human being commits a crime against another human being. Earthly justice has no problem in repaying the criminal by means of a temporally tensed state of imprisonment. One could argue, however, that, e.g., spending forty years in prison for the murder of a person is not an equivalent payment (as well as insufficient) because it is not comparable to what is involved in taking a person’s life. A bigger problem would be, e.g., if the criminal killed ten people. Even if one were to consider retribution through the death penalty, the death of one human would not compensate for the death of ten. Nevertheless, imprisonment is still used as the usual mode of punishment. That is a transition from a qualitative crime (assuming that every human has intrinsic value by virtue of being human) to a time-expressed penalty. Thus, the most approximate penalty, even if it falls short because of the ontological finitude of the FMA, is a temporally tensed punishment in time—a sempiternal punishment. It is the fairest way to repay God for the Sin that condemns us to an eternity away from God, the rejection of God as Lord of our lives. Rejecting GPB as Lord of our lives is an injustice of such magnitude that it can never be repaid. The debt is unpayable—qualitatively infinite.

persist in existence—one that the GPB would have allowed by permitting the annihilation of FMAs.

However, since the allowance of everlastingly unpunished injustice is incompatible with the holy and just nature of the GPB, such a scenario is logically and metaphysically impossible; there are no PWs in which the GPB exists and in which injustice remains everlastingly unpunished or unpaid.

Therefore, all FMAs would have to spend the rest of their existence suffering the consequences of their Sin. (That RP state would be hell, understood as ECT).

Yet, the GPB, out of His love, would necessarily desire all FMAs to be saved—i.e., to enter into a saving love relationship with the BWW. Despite the rebellion and Sin of the FMAs, the GPB may still will to save the FMAs from its everlasting consequences³⁵.

Every act of obedience and every good work that FMAs could perform does not serve to satisfy their debt, since such actions are required anyway (Anselm of Canterbury, 1926, p. 42). A GPB would have created FMAs morally good from the beginning; therefore, every good endeavor is simply what is naturally expected from them.

Only FMAs must satisfy their QI debt, but only the GPB is capable of rendering such satisfaction (Anselm of Canterbury, 1926, p. 58).

Therefore, only the GPB, by partaking in the essential nature of FMAs (Anselm of Canterbury, 1926, p. 59) as their legal representative (legal proxy), could offer perfect satisfaction. This satisfaction could be given as soon as He, assuming the essential nature of FMAs, offers His infinitely valuable life as a perfect compensation to Himself—the GPB³⁶.

Thus, only He who is QI could pay the price of a QI penalty, thereby satisfying the demands of His own perfect justice—sacrificing His own life, which possesses QI value³⁷. In doing

³⁵ In fact, the GPB may still will to save them from their Sin-caused alienation (Sin type 1(a)) from Him as well. This alienation (or ‘spiritual death’), extended in time due to their fallen nature, entails a necessary inclination to evil (or “slavery to sin”, see John 8:34; Titus 3:3; 2 Peter 2:19) that only Jesus can deliver Sinners from (John 8:31, 36; Romans 6:16-20).

³⁶ Thereby reestablishing justice in His universe and ensuring full debt payment for FMAs’ sin, making reconciliation possible for those who repent and trust in the GPB’s once-for-all Self-sacrifice, accomplished in space and time, for their salvation.

³⁷ In fact, according to Christian revelation, only Jesus Christ, who is the Perfect Infinite Being incarnate (John 1:1–3, 14, 18; Hebrews 1:3–4, 8, 10–12), was capable of satisfying the demands of God’s justice once for all (Hebrews 10:10, 12, 14).

so, He makes it possible for Sinners, instead of suffering the everlasting and just retributive consequences of their Sin, to be reconciled with Himself—the Perfect Being.

c. Temporal vs/and Everlasting. The logic of the biblical intermediate state—“temporal” hell, or Hades—is that of a provisional imprisonment with punishment. It functions analogously to a guilty criminal being held in prison while serving a sentence, awaiting final, irreversible capital punishment (e.g., the electric chair). In this analogy, the capital punishment corresponds to the ultimate, everlasting judgment. This distinction between two stages of punishment in the human realm may help illustrate the theological logic behind the two afterlife punishments: Hades (temporal) and Gehenna (eternal).

d. Metaphorical vs Literal. According to Christian theology, Gehenna is a punishment that will be experienced in both body and soul (Mathew 10:28) after the eschatological resurrection of the body (John 5:28–29; Revelation 20:5; 20:12–15), just as the sinner transgressed in both body and soul during earthly life. Regardless of whether the biblical images used to describe the hellish state (e.g., fire, darkness, worms) were intended as depictions of physical realities or symbolic representations of spiritual torment, they nonetheless point to terrible and undesirable realities—ones that transcend all earthly human experience. These images are not only vivid and terrifying but are framed within the context of conscious and consciously deserved RP. This punishment is endured by the wicked in a state of separation from the source of all goodness and blessing, i.e., God. Separated from the GPB, the damned FMAs will inevitably suffer in ways unimaginable in earthly life, where they daily received countless undeserved blessings. While the duration of hell punishment will be the same for all the damned—everlasting—their subjective experience of suffering will differ in degree, proportionate to their guilt.

Thus, in view of the eschatological resurrection of the wicked, as Vila-Ventura and Escuain (2013) observe, it would be a mistake to insist overmuch that the tormenting images are “mere symbols”. They rightly note that “images, symbols, etc., are used to express a fuller reality, not less, than that which the symbols themselves have.”

As for the biblical hellish images themselves and the metaphorical sense they may carry (despite their likely literal or analogical fulfilment), their meanings would be, at the very least, approximately as follows:

1. **Fire:** God’s judgment or His holy wrath against all injustice and sin (e.g., Hebrews 10:27).

2. **Darkness:** The absence of God’s light and goodness—separation from His presence (e.g., Genesis 1:2–3).

3. **Undying Worm:** A tormenting element of divine judgment that remains permanently present for the damned (see Mark 9:48).

Finally, it might well be the case that some of these images are meant to be taken literally or analogically, while others are metaphorical, expressing deeply spiritual or psychological agony. In my view, these images of punishment are to be understood analogically—i.e., while they retain a certain resemblance to the realities they are referring to, they go beyond literal description to signify experiences that surpass natural ones, being qualitatively different in nature.

e. Degrees of punishment.

Erickson (2014) observes:

The principle here seems to be, the greater our knowledge, the greater is our responsibility, and the greater will be our punishment if we fail in our responsibility. It may well be that the different degrees of punishment in hell are not so much a matter of objective circumstances as of subjective awareness of the pain of separation from God. ... To some extent, the different degrees of punishment reflect the fact that hell is God’s leaving a sinful human with the particular character that the person fashioned for himself or herself in this life. The misery one will experience from having to live with one’s wicked self eternally will be proportionate to one’s degree of awareness of precisely what one was doing when choosing evil. (chapter 58)

In response to Erickson’s point—which he quite reasonably qualifies by stating “to some extent”—I would add that ECT, as RP, should not be understood *merely* as a subjective experience of misery, such as “having to live with one’s wicked self eternally,” proportionate *only* “to one’s degree of awareness of precisely what one was doing when choosing evil.” Rather, the subjective experience of conscious torment would more accurately be proportionate to the degree of revelation the FMA possessed during their earthly life, and the extent to which they knowingly resisted or opposed that moral light by acting contrary to what they understood to be good and true.

III. ECT and Alternative Views

Below, I present the four main views on hell³⁸, followed by an analysis of their respective theological coherence and philosophical implications, thereby highlighting their strengths and weaknesses.

A. Four Views

1. *Traditionalist/Eternal Conscious Torment (ECT) View:*

Hell is an everlasting, conscious punishment to be inflicted upon any FMA who has Sinned against an infinitely just and holy God. According to Burk (2016), “the final state of the damned has at least three characteristics: (1) final separation, (2) unending experience, and (3) just retribution” (p. 21). This is the mainstream view throughout all Church history regarding the ultimate (eschatological) destiny of the wicked. It takes very seriously the holiness of God and the infinite gravity of Sin, seeing the logic of eternal conscious damnation as inevitable—unless the God-Man, Jesus Christ, pays the Sinner’s infinite debt, and the Sinner repents of their Sin and places their faith in Him to be legally justified before God (Romans 5:1), the Judge of the Universe. The ECT view holds that hell is a RP for human Sin, aligning closely with Anselm’s satisfaction theory and the Reformers’ penal substitution theory of atonement. This view of the nature of punishment aligns with *retributive* theories of justice, according to which, as Craig (2025) explains, “punishment is justified because the guilty deserve to be punished,” these being “retrospective, imposing punishment for crimes committed” (p. 454).

Craig (2025) also notes that “retributivism may be further distinguished as either positive or negative” (p. 454). He states:

While negative retributivism holds that the innocent should not be punished because they do not deserve it, the essence of retributive justice lies in positive retributivism, which holds that the guilty should be punished because they deserve it. What distinguishes

³⁸ For theological defenses, I will primarily use material from Sprinkle (2016), in which four Evangelical (Protestant) theologians discuss their views. They all accept the Bible as the supreme authority for Christian faith and conduct. They each hold a high view of Scripture, such that even the representative of annihilationism and the representative of universalism affirm that hell entails conscious misery of at least long duration. Therefore, clearly antibiblical views—which contradict many passages of Scripture—such as a form of annihilationism in which a person ceases to exist at the moment of death or upon arrival in hell, or a universalism in which everyone reaches heaven without first undergoing reconciliation with God through faith in Christ, will not be considered as legitimate competing views in this discussion.

retributivism as a theory of justice is the positive thesis that punishment of the guilty is an intrinsic good because the guilty deserve it. (Craig, 2025, p. 454)

Hence, advocates of ECT view believe that ECT analogously constitutes *an intrinsic good because the guilty deserve it*—a position coherent with God’s nature as an omnibenevolent, holy, just, and righteous being.

2. Issuantist (ISS)/Choice/Natural-Consequence/Separationist/Weak View: This is a variant of the ECT view that, as Baker (2015) observes, rejects “retributive interpretations of hell in favor of other theories where hell serves the purpose of restitution or reparation” (p. 8). Hell is an everlasting conscious misery to be experienced by any FMA who has Sinned by choosing separation from God—living their own way and seeking to remain lords of themselves.

Walls (2016) argues:

If hell is freely chosen by sinners who are given every opportunity to repent, but who persistently refuse the offer of grace, it is at least clear that they have chosen their own lot. Despite God’s sincere love for them, they have chosen to reject that love, and accordingly they experience the misery that inevitably results for persons who decisively reject the true end for which they were created. (p. 58)

According to Baker (2015), this view is known as ‘Issuantism’ because of ISS scholars’ “insistence that both heaven and hell must issue from the same divine quality—the love of God (Walls 1992; Buckareff; Plug 2005)” (p. 7). They believe love to be “a more foundational character quality than justice or wrath” (p. 7).

In fact, for Walls (2016) hell is eternal not because it is an imposed RP for sins, but because: some sinners persist in rejecting the love and grace of God for all eternity. Because God is love in his essential nature, his love to sinners never ceases, but those who resist his love refuse the only thing that can possibly make them happy, and consequently they remain in misery³⁹. (pp. 97-98)

³⁹ Ragland (n.d.) also provides an informative definition of this “free will view:”

The free will view is primarily a thesis about the purpose of hell. It teaches that God places the damned in hell *not* to punish them, but to honor the choices they have freely made. On this view, hell originates not so much from divine justice as from divine love.

Walls (2016) notes David Hart's (2003) observation of an Eastern Orthodox theological tradition that:

makes no distinction, essentially, between the fire of hell and light of God's glory and that interprets damnation as the soul's resistance to the beauty of God's glory, its refusal to open itself before the divine love, which causes Divine love to seem an exterior chastisement. (p. 98)

This perspective often leads ISS scholars to adopt a *Possible Escape* view of hell:

God's love is forever extended to those in hell, and it is possible that *some* of them *may* receive and decide to return home to the Father, as the prodigal son did when he finally came to see the things were much better back home. (Walls, 2016, p. 98, *my emphases*)

Thus, ISS distinguishes itself from other views by three *sine qua non* traits: (1) grounding both heaven and hell in God's love, (2) affirming LFW, and (3) rejecting RP models (Baker, 2015). Nonetheless, these essential features of ISS, along with some of its supplementary elements (see Baker, 2015, pp. 10-12) are sometimes also affirmed by proponents of alternative views on hell⁴⁰.

This weaker view of hell has become an alternative to the more traditional discourse and enjoys broad acceptance among contemporary Christian theologians, philosophers, and apologists. Its prominent defenders include scholars such as Swinburne (1983), Walls (1992), Davis (2010), Kvanvig (1993), and Wright (2008) (as cited in Baker, 2015), along with Wessling (2021) and Geach (1977) (as cited in Craig, 2025).

According to the free will view, one of God's purposes in creation is to establish genuine love-based relationships between God and humans, and within the human community. But love is a relation that can exist only between people who are genuinely free. Therefore, God gives people freedom in this life to decide for themselves whether or not they will reciprocate God's love by becoming the people God created them to be. People freely choose how they act, and through these choices they shape their moral character (a collection of stable tendencies to think, feel, and act, in certain ways). Those who develop a vicious character suffer psychologically, both in this life and in the life to come, for in the afterlife, people will keep the character they have developed in this life. So the suffering of hell consists (at the least) in living with one's own bad character.

⁴⁰ In fact, Baker (2015) observes that versions of TP and ECT may benefit from "the addition of some of the same supplements" introduced by ISS advocates, thereby "rendering some of their critique of retributive perspectives on hell unfounded" (p. 5).

3. *Annihilationist/Conditionalist/Terminal Punishment View (TP)*: As Stackhouse (2016) indicates, TP is the view that “hell is the situation in which those who do not avail themselves of the atonement made by Jesus in his suffering and death must make their own atonement by suffering and then death, separated from the sustaining life of God and thus disappearing from the cosmos” (pp. 61-62). This viewpoint, though still a minority position, has nonetheless gained prominent advocates among Bible-believing, conservative Christian theologians (Fudge & Peterson, 2000), and its influence is steadily growing within Protestant evangelical theological circles. Nevertheless, it remains a view that traditionalists—who represent the theological majority both today and throughout Christian history—regard as heterodox and not fully representative of the biblical teachings, especially those of the NT, concerning God, man, and sin. As for early Church history, annihilationism was an exceptionally rare view among the Church Fathers⁴¹. As in the ECT view, the TP perspective holds that hell is a RP. However, it differs from ECT in that it maintains the punishment must be proportional—adjusted to the crime committed, which is conceived as finite in nature. In Stackhouse’s (2016) words: “Finite beings can perform only a finite amount of sin, and therefore a finite amount of suffering is sufficient to atone for it” (p. 79). He continues: “The punishment fits the crime: God does not keep rebellious angels and humans alive forever, but only so long as is absolutely necessary for them to pay their debts and purge their guilt” (p. 80). Accordingly, it follows that an infinite punishment would be entirely disproportionate and, therefore, cruel, vindictive, and unjust—characteristics considered incompatible with a holy and just God. Conversely, according to the TP view, after receiving their deserved punishment—even if the consuming fire must burn forever and the worm never dies—the damned will ultimately cease to experience conscious torment and will cease to exist forever.

4. *Universalist⁴²/Restorationist/Ultime Reconciliation View*: Christian Universalism (CU), as Parry (2016) puts it, “is the view that in the end God will reconcile all people to himself

⁴¹ Perhaps Arnobius of Sicca (c. 300 A.D.) could best be credited with the paternity of Conditionalism. However, the great TP advocate Edward Fudge (2016) himself points out, “In reality he [Arnobius] said very little about final punishment. He directed his efforts against the Platonic worldview as such, especially against its anthropology” (p. 62).

⁴² Ragland (n.d.) provides a broader definition for universalism:

Universalism teaches that all people will ultimately be with God in heaven. There are two main versions of the view. According to necessary universalism, it is not possible for anyone to be eternally separated from God; necessarily, all are saved. According to contingent universalism, while it is possible that people could use their free will to reject God forever, no one will actually do this; eventually, everyone will say yes to God’s love. While it would be consistent with the basic universalist thesis to say that all people go

through Christ” (p. 101). The advocates of this position do believe that “there *is* eschatological punishment,” but they also affirm that “‘in the end’ there will be deliverance” (p. 101). Thus, CU teaches that all people will ultimately be saved—even after death and hell punishment. Although this is a minority view among Christian theologians, it is not, however, a novel view in historical terms. In fact, it has had supporters since ancient times, including some church fathers from the end of the second and the beginning of the third centuries A.D (Parry, 2016). Although Origen’s (3rd century) universalism—i.e., *apokatastasis*, which included the final salvation of condemned humans, demons, and even the devil—was condemned as heretical by councils in the 6th century A.D., the so-called CU position avoids the specific points of Origen’s teaching that were formally condemned in those councils’ canons. Thus, while its adherents are not technically “heretics,” they are generally considered heterodox by most Christian traditions. According to the CU, hell is a restorative punishment, not (*or not only*) a retributive one (Parry, 2016). Thus, it aligns more closely with *consequentialist* theories of justice, according to which, as Craig (2025) explains, “punishment is justified because of the extrinsic goods that may be realized thereby, such as deterrence of crime, sequestration of dangerous persons, and reformation of wrongdoers,” these being “prospective” in nature, “aiming to prevent crimes from being committed” (p. 454). Thus, this restorative CU interpretation of hell is more purgatorial⁴³ in nature. According to this position, *at some point*, each of the damned—after undergoing the restorative punishment necessary for their spiritual transformation—*will* repent and come to Christ. In this way, progressively, they will be reconciled with God and freely enter His kingdom⁴⁴.

immediately to heaven upon death, most universalists (in an effort to incorporate scriptural warnings about hell) insist that many people will undergo a temporary period of post-mortem suffering before entering heaven. This period of suffering, which could be seen as a temporary hell or as a kind of purgatory, could be motivated either by divine justice, as in the traditional view of hell, or by divine love, as in the free will view.

⁴³ Understood in terms of sanctification, not of satisfaction.

⁴⁴ A purely retributive version of CU could also be justified adopting a view that sins of sinners are finite and, therefore, the punishments must also have an end—provided that each and every one of the condemned, under sufficient divine grace that draws them to repentance and faith in Christ for conversion even in that state, willingly comes to Him and surrenders control of their souls to Jesus as their true King, Lord, and personal Savior of their being (Mark 1:15; Acts 16:31; Ephesians 2:8–9). That would be a case of universal postmortem conversion that does not rely on a restorative interpretation of hell. Otherwise, CU does not seem compatible with such purely retributive version *unless* it is accompanied by a personal postmortem conversion. No one can enter the kingdom of God without *first* repenting of having sought to be the king and lord of their own life (Mark 1:14–15; Acts 3:19; 20:21).

B. Strengths and Weaknesses⁴⁵

1. Traditionalist (ECT):

a. Theological Coherence.

i. Strengths:

a. ECT appears to be the position most consistent with the overall witness of Scripture and arguably enjoys the strongest exegetical support⁴⁶. Alternative views often seem to arise in reaction to ECT, and their proponents tend to adopt a revisionist posture—motivated in part by emotional discomfort with the idea of unending punitive suffering that surpasses any torment known on earth⁴⁷, and in part by theological concerns related to God’s love, justice, and mercy. Thus, some (ISS) claim that hell is simply the outcome of human free choice; others (TP) attempt to shorten its duration by appealing to ‘proportionality’; and still others (CU) try to make a reading that would allow for a happy ending for everyone.

b. As I argue in this paper, ECT accounts for the Bible’s systematic teaching regarding both God’s infinite attributes—such as justice, holiness, and eternity—and the gravity of human Sin (type 1), understood as offense and rebellion against the Source and Locus of all good and virtue.

ii. Weaknesses.

a. Exegetically, for ECT to hold, the word translated as “eternal”—the Greek term *aionios* (along with its Hebrew counterpart *olam*)—must be understood to denote “endless” or “never-ending” duration.

While ECT defenders rightly argue that *aionios* means “‘a period of unending duration’ or a time ‘without end’” (Burk, 2016, p. 28)—which aligns with the common understanding of “everlasting” *a parte post*—TP advocates insist that *aionios* often also means “of the age to come” (Stackhouse, 2016, p. 67). Stackhouse’s (2016) point, however, is that “‘eternal’ does *not always* mean ‘existing forever’” (p. 67, *my emphasis*).

⁴⁵ By no means do I intend to exhaust the list of benefits and drawbacks of each viewpoint; rather, I focus on those aspects I consider most relevant to the present study.

⁴⁶ For the sake of space and the main philosophical purpose of this paper, I will not provide a detailed exegetical analysis in support of ECT. See, however, the exegetical arguments and defenses presented by Burk (2016, pp. 17-43; 82-88; 128-133; 174-178), Peterson (in E. Fudge & Peterson, 2000—Peterson’s response to Conditionalism and chapters 7-9), and Gregg (2024, chapter 7).

⁴⁷ I agree with Burk (2016) that our emotional resistance to ECT reflects a “diminished view of sin—and thus of the judgment due to sin—because we have a diminished view of God.” He contends: “If we knew God better, we would not think like that” (p. 20).

He expounds:

the crucial distinction here is between, on the one hand, an event or an action that occurs for only a segment of time, and on the other, *the result* of that event or action that is indeed “without end.” Thus the event or action itself can properly be called “eternal” because of its everlasting implication. (Stackhouse, 2016, p. 67, *my emphasis*)

In my view, Stackhouse (2016) offers only two solid NT examples where *aionios* clearly carries the sense of “lasting forever.” The first is Hebrews 9:11–12, where “eternal redemption,” in context, means “once for all” (p. 68). The second is Mark 3:28–29, where “an eternal sin” is best understood as one that “has eternal consequences” (pp. 68–69).

Thus, if *aionios* were consistently interpreted as referring to an everlasting *result* rather than a specific (unending) duration throughout its NT usage, the exegetical foundation for affirming ECT would be significantly weakened—unless, of course, the context clearly compelled the interpreter to read *aionios* as denoting unending duration in several key passages⁴⁸.

In any case, Gregg’s (2024) observation may be helpful:

George Milligan and James Hope Moulton said that *aionios* “depicts that of which the horizon is not in view, whether the horizon be at an infinite distance . . . or whether it lies no farther than the span of a Caesar’s life.” This is essentially identical to the meaning of the Hebrew *olam*, and obviously does not require that the thing, of which the end is *beyond our vision*, must necessarily go on into endless eternity. *It might, but it needn’t.* (chapter 5, *my emphases*)

If I were to offer a general definition—one that would later need to be clarified by the specific context in which the terms *olam*, *aion*, and *aionios* appear—I would concur with F. F. Bruce, as quoted in Gregg (2024), that these terms do not inherently denote endlessness. Rather, “these in themselves express indefinite duration, but the context or the inherent sense may make the indefiniteness more explicit” (chapter 5).

⁴⁸ Among the clearest texts that may help disambiguate the meaning of *aionios* are Revelation 20:10 alongside 14:11, and Matthew 25:41 alongside 25:46. I discuss these below in my criticism of TP.

b. In my view, the strongest biblical proof-text against ECT in favor of TP *could* be 2 Peter 2:6: “if by turning the cities of Sodom and Gomorrah to ashes he condemned them to extinction, making them an example of what is going to happen to the ungodly” (*ESV*, 2016).

Nevertheless, it is hermeneutically mistaken to construct doctrine from a single verse. Sound hermeneutical principles require that obscure or ambiguous passages be interpreted in light of the clearer, more explicit ones. Before proceeding with interpretation, it is necessary to consider the textual variants found in ancient manuscripts and the possible alternative readings of the Greek. In fact, this is a case involving a significant textual variant, which translators acknowledge in a footnote: “Some manuscripts *an example to those who were to be ungodly*” (Footnote to 2 Peter 2:6, *ESV*, 2016). Therefore, it would be unwise to draw definitive conclusions too hastily. If the autograph of 2 Peter indeed read as indicated in the footnote, there would be no valid basis for inferring the annihilation of the ungodly from this verse.

Yet Sprinkle (2016, p. 194), following Stackhouse (2016, p. 71)—who cites the first aforementioned version of 2 Peter 2:6—highlights this verse and pairs it with its parallel in Jude 7: “just as Sodom and Gomorrah and the surrounding cities, which likewise indulged in sexual immorality and pursued unnatural desire, serve as an example by undergoing a punishment of eternal fire” (*ESV*, 2016), arguing that “it cannot be interpreted with exegetical honesty to support” ECT (p. 194).

In contrast, I would argue that, since Jude 7 can reasonably be interpreted in either direction, 2 Peter 2:6 should be read in light of the clearer passages—i.e., those NT texts cited by Burk (2016) in support of ECT. This is not exegetical dishonesty—I fully acknowledge the difficulty posed by 2 Peter 2:6—but rather a matter of adhering to the principles of historical-grammatical hermeneutics, which all conservative Protestant-evangelical theologians, including Stackhouse, Parry, Walls, and Sprinkle, hold to.

c. Although this does not undermine the theological plausibility of ECT itself, it is worth noting that defending ECT as a just punishment within a Calvinist framework appears inconsistent. I fully agree with Walls (2016), who states that “the doctrine of hell is morally indefensible, given theological determinism” (p. 57)—i.e., because “the sins that merit eternal punishment on this view are sins that the damned were determined by God to commit” (Walls, 2013, p. 496). Thus, while I agree with Burk’s (2016, pp. 17-43) theological (and philosophical) defense of ECT, I

believe Walls' critical questions toward Burk's presumed theological determinism (see Walls, 2016, pp. 56-59) is well-founded⁴⁹.

b. Philosophical Implications.

i. Strengths:

a. If ECT is true, the achievement of perfect retributive justice (RJ) is guaranteed, and PBT *makes coherent sense*.

The following argument seeks to set forth the logical reasoning underlying this claim:

P1. If ECT is true, then there is ultimately deserved retribution for evil.

P2. If there is ultimately deserved retribution for evil, then there exists an ultimate morally just Judge who administers justice in the universe.

P3. If there exists an ultimate morally just Judge, then there exists a Guarantor of ultimate RJ.

P4. If a Guarantor of ultimate RJ exists, then ultimate RJ is guaranteed.

P5. If ultimate RJ is guaranteed, then this is expected under PBT.

C. Therefore, if ECT is true, PBT makes coherent sense.

b. If PBT is true, then ECT *makes coherent sense*.

Burk (2016) illustrates this point with his *Parable on Punishment and Justice* (see pp. 18-20). This is a reconstructed argument underlying Burk's parable:

P1. The moral seriousness of harming a being depends on that being's value (e.g., we see that harming a baby for fun is far worse than harming a grasshopper for fun, even though the cruel act of "pulling the legs off" *per se* is the same).

P2. God is infinitely more valuable than any creature (including humans).

P3. Infinitely serious sins deserve infinitely severe punishment.

C. Therefore, sin against God is infinitely serious and deserves infinite punishment (ECT).

⁴⁹ I believe, however, that Walls is entirely mistaken in his critique of Burk's *Parable of Punishment and Justice* (see pp. 18-20), particularly when he asserts that "God is so far above us in power, glory, and moral perfection that we are utterly incapable of harming him" (p. 56). In Scripture, it is evident that idolatry (forbidden in the first and second commandments) and blasphemy (forbidden in the third commandment) are grave offenses against God. Therefore, it is not necessary for human beings to be "infinite" in order to cause moral offense to God; it is sufficient that we are FMAs, created in His image yet capable of rebellion and ingratitude (see Romans 1:18-32). If there were no real offense against God's honor, justice, and holiness, there would be no need for atoning sacrifices whatsoever. Consequently, the sacrifice of Jesus Christ—the incarnate God—would be legally unnecessary as well (see Hebrews 10).

ii. Weaknesses:

a. If ECT is true, the punished individuals will undergo everlasting suffering, thereby perpetuating the subjective experience of pain for all eternity *a parte post*. This, of course, may appear cruel—and therefore improper for the GPB—until one considers that the imposition of hellish punishment, which results in such a perpetual experience of misery, is both *a good*⁵⁰, insofar as it constitutes a RP that the evildoer deserves, and *a choice*⁵¹ of the FMA, who voluntarily rejected the Perfect Being as Lord of their life, having been able to enter into a personal love/friendship relationship with Him during their earthly life.

b. Potentially, a real weakness of ECT could arise, however, under an interpretation of ECT in which the damned in hell retain LFW, thereby preserving their moral responsibility before God. This approach could serve as an additional argument to the one previously defended⁵² regarding the necessity of conscious and everlasting punishment. It would clarify how the inhabitants of hell, insofar as they persist in hating and rejecting God, could continuously accrue further guilt for sins (type 2) *ad infinitum*, thus remaining perpetually indebted to God due to their ongoing evil⁵³.

Nonetheless, this very notion of LFW in hell—though lacking exegetical support—would philosophically open the door to a possible escape. If the damned, as FMAs, were to exercise their LFW in repentance and turn to God, then, assuming the righteousness of Christ is imputed to them by faith, they ought to be able to escape hell and enter heaven, as proposed in the ISS model. In such a scenario, moreover, RP would justly cease, for the FMA would have received divine forgiveness through the satisfactory and substitutionary atonement offered once for all by the God-man on the cross. In such a case—contrary to the teachings of Scripture (e.g., in Mathew 25:41)—hell *could* serve as a reformatory for some, thereby no longer functioning as a place whose only teleological function is the punishment of the wicked.

⁵⁰ An “intrinsic good”, recalling Craig’s (2025) defense of RP.

⁵¹ While I defer from pure ISS, I certainly believe that ISS is partly right regarding the elective aspect of the FMA in relation to its eternal destiny. I simply hold that such an election is ‘sealed’ forever at death, and that the individual is thereafter deprived of LFW. From that point on, the individuals possess only *compatibilist* freedom, being unable to overcome their own fallen nature. Once LFW is annulled, the individuals’ moral responsibility before God as Judge is likewise annulled, since everything the lost individual does consciously from that moment forward is no longer considered moral evil. They simply get what they *deserve* and what they *chose* while they were still FMAs.

⁵² See section II.B.2 (pp. 24-27).

⁵³ This is, e.g., the first of two strategies proposed by Craig to explain why ECT punishment makes sense and why TP and ISS’ modifications of the traditional view seem unnecessary (see Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34).

2. *Issuantist (ISS)*:

a. Theological Coherence.

i. Strengths:

a. ISS affirms LFW, which arguably underlies all Scripture, where God persistently calls individuals to repentance and obedience to His commands, under the threat of punishment for disobedience (e.g., Genesis 2:17; Deuteronomy 30:15–19; Ezekiel 18:30–32). As such, ISS rejects theological determinism (i.e., Calvinism). As Walls (2013) observes, “the denial of libertarian freedom exacerbates the problem of hell, for the sins that merit eternal punishment on this view are sins that the damned were determined by God to commit”⁵⁴ (p. 496).

ii. Weaknesses:

a. According to Scripture, God “will by no means clear the guilty” (Exodus, 34:7, *ESV*, 2016). God cannot hold the guilty innocent; His justice is clearly retributive throughout the biblical narrative. Infernal punishment, therefore, is likewise retributive (Romans 2:5; Matthew 25:46). ISS conflicts with this view, for it reduces the retributive separation from God (2 Thessalonians 1:9) to a mere consequence of the FMA’s own choice to separate himself from God. While this element of choice is indeed present⁵⁵—inasmuch as the FMA chose a life independent of God—the primary reason for the loss of God’s *common grace*⁵⁶ in hell is, ultimately, their Sin.

It is worth reproducing here Craig’s (2025) theological critique of this view:

In general, the natural consequences view of God’s response to sin is biblically inadequate. Certainly sin is regarded in the Scriptures as self-destructive in its consequences, but God’s response to sin is not reducible to permitting sin’s natural consequences. Rather God imposes justly deserved punishments in response to sin. Already in the story of the fall in Gen 3, the words “you shall surely die” (*môṭ tāmûṭ*) occur repeatedly in the legal collections of the OT condemning criminals to death. Victor Hamilton notes that all of the *môṭ tāmûṭ* passages in the OT deal with either a punishment for sin or an untimely death as the result

⁵⁴ While I strongly disagree with Burk (2016), who asserts that “God does not love those who are in hell” (p. 131), I firmly agree with Walls (2016), who rightly observes that “God is love in His essential nature; His love for sinners never ceases” (p. 98).

⁵⁵ Therefore, I agree with C.S. Lewis’s (1945/2019) famous quote: “There are only two kinds of people in the end: those who say to God, ‘Thy will be done,’ and those to whom God says, in the end, ‘Thy will be done.’” (chapter 9, para. 67). My point is that people make this choice *on earth*, not in the afterlife.

⁵⁶ God’s undeserved blessings—extended universally to all humanity regardless of their faith, belief, or moral standing (e.g., Matthew 5:45 and Acts 14:17).

of punishment, so that in the story of the fall the expression clearly conveys the announcement of a death sentence by divine or royal decree. In the NT the forensic language is pervasive, especially in Paul's treatment of condemnation and justification in Romans. Recall Dunn's conclusion "that God's righteousness towards the peoples he has created includes wrath and judgment as well as faithfulness and salvation is clearly implicit in the sequences Rom. 1.16–18 and 3.3–6." Those who deny that *dikaiosynē* is a forensic term pay insufficient attention to Rom 4.4–5, "where the forensic background is clear in the allusion to the legal impropriety of a judge 'justifying the ungodly'." (p. 460)

b. While ISS appears to imply a possible escape, Scripture makes no mention of such an outcome; rather, it consistently affirms the everlasting, punitive, and irreversible nature of hell (see Matthew 8:12; 25:10–12; 25:46; Mark 9:48; Luke 13:24–29; 16:26; John 5:28–29; 2 Thessalonians 1:9; Revelation 14:11). The time for repentance and coming to Christ is now: "it is appointed for man to die once, and after that comes judgment" (Hebrews 9:27, *ESV*, 2016).

c. It is difficult to conceive how there could be *degrees of punishment* in a state of separation from God *chosen* by the person. Who determines the proportionality of such punishment? Not all the damned committed evils of equal gravity or equal quantity during their earthly lives. The doctrine of degrees of punishment is *not merely* theological; it is also a principle of justice grounded in common sense, human juridical practice, and our moral intuition about justice.

b. Philosophical Implications:

i. Strengths:

a. If some version of ISS is true, and heaven and hell are grounded in God's love rather than in retributive wrath, then hell becomes the natural consequence of the FMAs' free choice to self-exclude from God's presence. This addresses the incompatibility objection, which claims that a loving God could not permit everlasting torment.

b. If some version of ISS is true, and individuals possess LFW, then their choices are genuinely self-determined. This addresses the critique of Calvinistic determinism, particularly concerning the predestination of the lost.

c. If some version of ISS is true, and God does not punish individuals in a retributive sense, then the suffering experienced in hell results from the self-imposed separation from God's gracious presence—a condition the FMAs have freely chosen, thereby harming themselves. This addresses the proportionality objection to ECT.

As pointed out in regard to this nuanced perspective, *basic* ISS implies accepting three *sine qua non* propositions: (1) heaven and hell are grounded in God's love, (2) individuals possess LFW, and (3) God does not punish individuals in a retributive sense (see Baker, 2015). Although, as Baker (2015) argues (see pp. 8-9), pure formulations of ISS “do not provide an adequate answer to the problem of hell,” ISS scholars have introduced “a wide range of” supplementary theses to strengthen the basic model (p. 5). He maintains that “some of these supplemented versions succeed in presenting reasonable answers to the problem of hell” (p. 5). The following is Baker's (2015) list of such supplementary theses added to the basic ISS model:

1. **Not-so-Nasty Thesis:** “People in hell are content with their situation, since they have received what they genuinely want” (p. 10). Held by: C. S. Lewis and S. Davis.

2. **Less-than-Human Thesis:** Inhabitants of hell lose their humanity. Held by: C. S. Lewis and N. T. Wright.

3. **Nearly-Empty Thesis:** Hell will be inhabited by only a “small number of irredeemably evil beings” (p. 11). Held by: E. Stump.

4. **Extra Chance Theses:** Various forms allowing people one or more postmortem opportunities to be saved. Held by: J. Walls, E. Stump, S. Davis, Swinburne, Buckareff and Plug.

5. **Fixed Character Thesis:** “The formation of an evil character explains how people can choose to remain in hell” (p. 11). Held by: Swinburne and J. Kvanvig.

6. **Irrationality Thesis:** “God allows people to make irrational choices, even if those choices entail that they end up in hell” (p. 12). Held by: Davis, Swinburne and Walls.

As I see it, the true strength of basic ISS is its second trademark, i.e., (2) individuals possess LFW. This consideration is particularly important in light of the common objection raised against ECT when defended within an Augustinian-Calvinist framework. In contrast, ISS takes an Arminian approach⁵⁷, which I affirm—at least insofar as it pertains to this present life. I contend, however, that the damned do not retain LFW in hell, as I argue later in this thesis.

⁵⁷ As Talbott (2022) explains, Arminianism is “named after Jacobus Arminius (1560-1609) for his opposition to the very idea of limited election”. Within Arminian theology, “God's perfecting (or electing) love extends to all created

ii. Weaknesses:

a. If ISS is true, then its trademarks (1) and (3) are true, i.e., (1) heaven and hell are grounded in God’s love, and (3) God does not punish individuals in a retributive sense.

If that is the case, ISS seems to imply what Wessling (2021) called “The Identity Thesis” (p. 148). As Craig (2025) informs, “The thesis is that ‘God’s love is identical to His moral goodness,’ such that ‘God possesses no moral attribute that is not essentially and most fundamentally a matter of love.’” (p. 453). This view is problematic, however, for several reasons that Craig (2025) adduces:

1. The Bible portrays God’s moral character as including both love and justice, not reducing righteousness to love alone (Exodus 34:7; Romans 1:32). (p. 454)

2. Retributive Justice—punishing the guilty because they deserve it—is central to God’s nature, even sans creation (Genesis 18:25; Romans 9:14). (p. 455)

3. “Proponents of the Identity Thesis tend to endorse, explicitly or implicitly, a consequentialist theory of divine justice. For they insist that God’s sole purpose in punishing wrong-doers is reformative, rather than retributive” (p. 455). Consequentialists, therefore, regard punishment as justified only insofar as it serves some future good. God’s judgment, however, “is described in the Bible as ultimately eschatological. The ungodly are ‘storing up wrath’ for themselves for God’s final day of judgment (Rom. 2.5)” (p. 458). RJ alone adequately accounts for such a final judgment, since eschatological punishment can no longer be reformative. Consequentialism, therefore, fails in an eternal framework. Therefore, the thesis that God’s justice is purely love-driven is false.

4. Hell, as mere “natural consequence,” contradicts Scripture’s emphasis on divine wrath and judgment (1 Corinthians 11:27–31; 2 Peter 2:1–16; Revelation 16). (pp. 459-460; Wessling, 2021, p. 152)

5. The Identity Thesis cannot explain eternal punishment, since love alone cannot justify irreversible retribution (cf. Romans 2:5; 12:19; Hebrews 10:29). (pp. 456-460)

b. If ISS is true, then its trademark (3) is true, i.e., (3) God does not punish individuals in a retributive sense.

persons equally, but that love can be thwarted by factors, such as certain human choices, over which God has no direct causal control.”

This non-retributivist version of hell, however, faces potentially an objection even from PBT, i.e., RJ might be an inherent characteristic of the GPB.

As I have argued above, RJ clearly appears to be an essential attribute of the God of the Bible. However, I believe that, apart from any exegetical considerations, we can still make the following argument from PBT alone against ISS:

P1. There is *no logical incompatibility* between the existence of a Perfect Being and one of His essential attributes being RJ; therefore, it is *possible* that the GPB is retributivist. The burden of proof lies on anyone who wishes to deny such compatibility.

P2. At least from a human perspective and based on the philosophy of law, we know of two main types of justice: *consequentialist* and *retributivist* (Craig, 2018b, p. 67). Lacking other options, we must use these categories to understand what it means to say that God is inherently just.

P3. “Consequentialist theories of justice hold that punishment is justified because of the extrinsic goods that may be realized by punishing wrongdoers, such as deterrence of crime, sequestration of dangerous persons, and reformation of wrongdoers” (Craig, 2025, p. 454).

P4. ISS affirms that hell is a non-retributive form of divine punishment—something theologically required by the biblical language of punishment—yet explicitly rejects retributivism. Thus, having denied retributive grounds for divine punishment, ISS is left with consequentialism as the only remaining option within the framework of the philosophy of law.

P5. Eternal punishment, even as held by ISS—i.e., eternal conscious misery—is not explicable within a consequentialist framework, since such punishment does not result in any of the extrinsic goods that consequentialist theories of justice aim to achieve.

C1. Therefore, if there is ultimately an eternal conscious misery as a just divine punishment (as ISS affirms), it must be grounded in a RJ intrinsic to the character of the GPB⁵⁸. (From P2, P4, and P5)

⁵⁸ Craig (ReasonableFaithOrg, 2024) presents an interesting argument for how God could be eternally and essentially a retributivist:

God’s justice is expressed within the Trinity just as fully as His love. God would never act unjustly toward one member of the Trinity. One of the principles of *negative retributive justice* is that the innocent should never be punished. So, in the absence of sinners, God’s justice—like His love—is perfectly expressed within the Trinity itself. (30:47-31:26, as transcribed and adapted by the author, *my emphasis*)

C2. Thus, ISS, being consequentialist by virtue of its rejection of retributivism, is *probably* false. (From P4, P5, and C1)

c. If *basic* ISS is true, ISS is not sufficient to provide an “adequate answer to the problem of hell” (Baker, 2015, p. 5).

Baker (2015) argues that *basic* ISS, defined by the three trademarks discussed above, carries with it some problematic implications:

1. Culpability: Even if hell is the result of the exercise of LFW, one could blame God for having designed a system in which finite sins lead to infinite suffering. This challenges ISS’s claim that hell is purely “the natural consequence of a person’s free rejection of God” (p. 5), since God’s design of such disproportionate outcomes (e.g., eternal conscious misery) still implies moral responsibility on His part. No rational being would freely choose such an undesirable, everlasting fate. (p. 5)

2. Finality: If people in hell remain free, they could freely “leave hell”. Likewise, the godly could “freely leave heaven”. Thus, “If people are free to leave heaven or hell, then one’s destiny has no sense of finality that is an integral part of any Christian understanding of the final judgment.” (p. 9)

3. Gratitude: “God gets the credit for those who are saved, but not the blame for those who are damned” (p. 9). This form of ISS creates an asymmetrical responsibility. (p. 9)

4. Redundance: ISS reduces God’s role to a mere enforcer of human choices, making Him largely redundant. Accordingly, Moltmann characterizes ISS views of hell as ‘atheistic’. (p. 9)

d. If ISS is true, PBT *does not make coherent sense*.

ISS fails to fully appreciate divine perfection and the gravity of Sin. Even if sins (type 2) could somehow be paid for through suffering equivalent to the harm or evil FMAs caused throughout their earthly lives, it is clear that they would remain infinitely indebted to God for Sin (type 1). The rationale is as follows: the debt incurred by rejecting the Perfect Being as Lord of one’s life—by resisting His lordship whenever an FMA perceives His existence, presence, voice, or calling through His general revelation in nature and conscience—is an offense of infinite magnitude, impossible to repay in a way that satisfies divine justice or compensates for the offense against God’s holiness. There is nothing morally worse than rejecting the Good in person. This applies to every human being at an age of consciousness in general.

However, rejecting the Perfect Being incarnated for our salvation—about whom people come to know through the Gospel message (that He came to pay our debt to God through His death on the cross, and that He was seen alive by eyewitnesses after His resurrection)—even if the individual does not have a high degree of epistemic confidence in its truth, the mere fact of hearing this message about someone who allegedly lived on earth, and yet refusing to investigate it by all available means, is an attitude toward God that is condemnable in a much more serious and intense way. At this point, it is no longer a question of general revelation, but of special revelation in history. If, in addition, the person has had a religious experience associated with this God—or perhaps witnessed a miracle or received healing—this would further aggravate their guilt and punishment.

3. Annihilationist (TP):

a. Theological Coherence.

i. Strengths:

a. The main argumentative strength of TP lies in the inherent vagueness of the terms *olam* and *aionios*—the Hebrew and Greek words commonly translated as “eternal.” As already discussed above⁵⁹, these terms can denote not only proper *a parte ante* eternity or *a parte post* everlastingness, but also the *result* or consequence of an event or action⁶⁰ (Stackhouse, 2016).

Stackhouse (2016) argues, e.g., that while “when God is said to be eternal, Scripture clearly means ‘forever,’” there are also “ordinances, rituals, and institutions” described as *olam* in the OT that do not carry the same sense of literal endlessness (p. 66). In the case of the Passover or the rites for the ordination of priests, *olam* denotes the obligation to “observe the rite as a perpetual ordinance” (pp. 66-67). However, when Solomon declared that the temple would be a place for God to ‘dwell in forever,’ the expression was likely hyperbolic rather than literal, as it is well understood that “no human building could last forever” (p. 67).

b. Another strength, related to the one previously discussed, lies in the OT use of words such as “fire and sulfur,” “unquenchable fire,” “furnace,” “smoke,” and “darkness,”⁶¹ that later are repeated in the New, suggesting semantic continuity. Notably, in the OT, the events in which these

⁵⁹ See *Weaknesses* of ECT (pp. 34-37).

⁶⁰ Moreover, as Gregg (2024) argues, these terms are used in a range of ways, including: (1) “The thing described is everlasting, eternal (literal or hyperbole)”;

(2) “The thing described lasts for an age, or a long time (long-enduring)”;

(3) “The thing described pertains to a given age, or to ‘the age to come’”; and (4) “The thing described is of divine origin—inherent in (or proceeding from) the eternal God” (chapter 5, headings).

⁶¹ See E. Fudge & Peterson, 2000, chapter 2, to see Fudge’s argumentation on this.

expressions appear—particularly in the context of divine judgment—refer to cities and peoples destined to suffer *physical* destruction by “fire”, and thus, from the perspective of those living on earth, they would indeed cease to exist. To take only one example—the use of “unquenchable fire”—Edward Fudge (in E. Fudge & Peterson, 2000), the main defender of TP, argues that “throughout Scripture⁶² unquenchable fire signifies fire that cannot be extinguished or resisted and that therefore consumes until nothing is left (Is 34:10–11; Ezek 20:47–48; Amos 5:6; Mt 3:12)” (chapter 2).

ii. Weaknesses⁶³:

a. To be fair and to balance the aforementioned arguments for TP, it is important to recognize that the OT contains very *limited revelation* regarding the afterlife—both the intermediate state and the eschatological one. It is, therefore, understandable that the ‘eternal’ aspect of suffering—both of soul and body—was not clearly emphasized through these symbols and metaphors of divine judgment. Only with the coming of Jesus in the NT do we gain a clear understanding of the eternal destiny of both the righteous in the Kingdom of Heaven and the wicked in hell. Consequently, it is methodologically (and hermeneutically) mistaken to apply *semantically constrained* OT categories onto the fuller NT revelation, which discloses the everlasting states of both groups.

Whereas it is true that the OT, on its own, leaves its readers at best with uncertainty—or at most, with a notion of temporality that carries everlasting repercussions—the NT appears to point clearly to an eternity without end. Notably, the same expression translated as “forever and ever,” used to describe God (1:6; 4:9–10; 5:13; 7:12; 10:6; 15:7), His people (22:5), His/Christ’s kingdom and reign (11:15), and the worship of Christ (5:13) in the book of Revelation, is also used to describe the fate of the damned: “And the smoke of their torment goes up forever and ever, and they have no rest, day or night” (Revelation 14:11; cf. 20:10, *ESV*, 2016). The same language is used for the symbolic city of Babylon, whose inhabitants persecuted Christians (19:3; cf. 17:6). Similarly, in the words of Jesus in Matthew 25:46, the same term “everlasting” (*aionios*) is applied

⁶² I believe he should have said, instead, “throughout the Old Testament,” so as not to beg the question regarding whether that is the case in the NT as well.

⁶³ Despite my criticism of and disagreement with TP—and my stronger conviction, both exegetically and philosophically, in the truth of ECT—I acknowledge that TP is an exegetically legitimate interpretation. This contrasts with CU or ISS with its possible escape version, whose defenders must either overlook the clearly retributive nature of God’s justice in Scripture or, in the case of CU, read into certain texts a hope of universal redemption that neither Christ announced nor the NT writers ever enunciated.

parallelly to both, the righteous and the wicked. These passages seem clearly to imply everlasting duration for both the members of both groups.

b. Apart from the use of the meaning and use of the word “eternal” and the incorporation of OT symbols of divine judgment in the New, TP advocates find support for their position with another key argument—i.e., that when Scripture speaks of “destruction” or “death,” it generally means “termination” (Stackhouse, 2016, p. 69).

The problem, however, is that this is not the whole story. In Genesis 2:17, God warned Adam and Eve that they would die if they ate from the tree of the knowledge of good and evil. When they did so (Genesis 3), they indeed died—not physically, but spiritually, as is evident both from the immediate context and from NT commentary (e.g., Romans 5:12). Notably, this is the first mention of death in the Bible.

The NT further teaches that every person, prior to believing in Christ, is “dead in [their] trespasses and sins” (Ephesians 2:1) and subject to divine wrath for living in accordance with their own desires (Ephesians 2:3), until they are made spiritually alive by grace (Ephesians 2:4–5). Moreover, as I argued above⁶⁴, Scripture teaches that prior to the eschatological resurrection, there exists an *intermediate state* in which the soul remains conscious after physical death. For believers, this entails being “in paradise” or “the third heaven” (Luke 23:43; 2 Corinthians 12:2, 4), “present with the Lord” (2 Corinthians 5:8), which Paul describes as “far better” than life on earth (Philippians 1:23). For nonbelievers, that state entails being “in Hades” in a conscious “torment” (Luke 16:23; see also 16:19–31⁶⁵). All of this clearly contradicts the notion of “death” as sheer termination.

Similarly, the NT usage of *apollunai*—often translated as “destroy” or “perish”—does not imply annihilation, but rather ruin or perdition. This is evident in Jesus’ parables: the *lost* wineskins (Mark 2:22), the *lost* sheep, coin, and son (Luke 15) were never annihilated. They were lost, not extinguished. Jesus came “to seek and save the lost”—not the nonexistent (Luke 19:10). Likewise, in John 3:16, the one who does not believe is said to “perish,” but the use of *apollunai*

⁶⁴ See section II.A.1 (p. 19) and II.A.2 (p. 20).

⁶⁵ Many dispute whether this passage should be read merely as a parable (see Gregg, 2024, chapter 4), but there are intra-textual reasons to favor a more literal interpretation:

Scripture does not identify the story as a parable, and Jesus, in mentioning the proper names of two individuals (Lazarus, Abraham), introduces a feature not found in any other of Jesus’s recorded parables. These factors have inclined many to conclude that this is not one of Jesus’s parables, but that He is relating an actual case of two real men who died. (Gregg, 2024, chapter 4)

in the context of salvation and condemnation clearly refers to being lost or ruined—not annihilated. Furthermore, I would argue that there are no good reasons to interpret it otherwise.

The other term for “destruction” is *olethros*. It is found in 2 Thessalonians 1:9: “They will suffer the punishment of eternal destruction, away from the presence of the Lord and from the glory of his might” (*ESV*, 2016). According to Burk (2016), “Paul is the only NT author to use this term, and in none of its other uses does it mean ‘cease to exist’ (cf. 1 Cor. 3:5; 1 Thess. 5:3; 1 Tim. 6:9)” (p. 35).

While *prima facie* “destruction,” as Gregg (2024) notes, “may sound ... like extinction, it may also convey the idea of ruin, not annihilation”(chapter 7). For instance, “1 Timothy 6:9–10 ... suggests the ruination ... that comes upon one who inordinately loves money” (chapter 7). Likewise, *olethros* “is used by Paul in 1 Corinthians 5:5, where the ‘destruction of the flesh’ is seen as a means by which a sinner’s spirit might ultimately be saved”⁶⁶ (chapter 8).

c. TP—or perhaps Stackhouse (2016) personally—boldly maintains a view that, in my assessment, is both biblically mistaken and, notably, unsupported by any clear scriptural evidence (see pp. 61-81): i.e., that the *suffering* and *death* of a sinful individual can somehow *atone for* their own sins (see pp. 61, 64, 66, 76, 77, 79). ‘Paying’ for sin in a judicial or retributive sense is one thing; to assert that true reparation or compensation has taken place—as if the sin were effectively covered or erased by that sinners’ suffering (and death)—is quite another⁶⁷. Scripture never teaches that personal suffering can atone for sin⁶⁸.

⁶⁶ This unusual comment concerns the case of a member of a local church who committed an act of immorality so scandalous that even the surrounding pagan society found it shocking. Paul concludes that the individual should undergo a period of disciplinary excommunication, during which his physical well-being would probably be *ruined*, with the ultimate goal being the spiritual salvation of the person.

⁶⁷ This tendency to view suffering as having atoning value was already identified by James White in his debate with two TP proponents on *Unbelievable?* (Brierly, 2009), where he observed that their position “would require the idea that the suffering of the one justly condemned would somehow have propitiatory power (merit) before God” (39:27-39:40, as transcribed by the author). This appears to be the underlying assumption of TP.

⁶⁸ Nevertheless, I would like to give the author the benefit of the doubt. Perhaps Stackhouse (2016) is using the word *atone* or *atonement* in a non-biblical or metaphorical sense, and I may be misunderstanding his point. Still, given his claim to be exegetically and biblically grounded (p. 66), I find it surprising—first, that he would hold such a theologically foreign idea, and second, that he would fail to support such a repeated and central claim throughout the chapter in which he lays out and defends his position.

b. Philosophical Implications.

i. Strengths:

a. If *retributive* TP is true, then punishment in hell seems to be reasonable and just, even by earthly legal standards. On earth, there are no punishments that last “*forever and ever.*” Therefore, TP *seems* philosophically unobjectionable.

ii. Weaknesses:

a. If TP is true, PBT *does not make coherent sense.*

As with ISS, TP also fails to fully appreciate divine perfection and the gravity of sin; therefore, my philosophical criticism (d) of ISS applies here in precisely the same way⁶⁹.

b. If TP is true, it diverges from all three Jordan Wessling’s values of love: *existence*, *flourishing*, and *friendship*.

Mullins (2022) argues in his paper that Wessling’s (2020) value account of love—contrary to classical theism—not only makes “God’s love” for humans “perfectly rational,” but also explains “why it is perfectly rational for God to have desires about our well-being, flourishing, and why God desires friendship with humans” (p. 3, Helda electronic reprint). Mullins then critically analyzes views on hell using two criteria: (1) Wessling’s (2020) value account of love and (2) the biblical *ultimate defeat of evil* (Revelation 20-22), and concludes that while TP satisfies (2), it fails to meet any aspect of (1).

He argues:

First, God cannot be said to value the existence of a person if God eradicates her from existence. Second, God cannot be said to value the flourishing of a person if God eradicates her from existence. After all, a person cannot flourish if she does not exist. Third, God cannot be said to value friendship with a person if God eradicates her from existence. One usually does not put people in the friendzone by annihilating them from existence. I gather that if God annihilates you from existence, He is just not that into you. Hence, Annihilationism diverges from all three values of love. (Mullins, 2022, pp. 5-6, Helda electronic reprint)

⁶⁹ Thus, see the philosophical implication (d) in the *Weaknesses* of ISS (pp. 44-45) where I explore this criticism.

I entirely agree with Mullins' (2022) conclusion: "There is sufficient reason to reject annihilationism. So we need to look elsewhere to see how God can ultimately defeat evil without diverging from love" (pp. 5-6, Helda electronic reprint).

c. If TP is true, strangely enough, then 'eternal life' and 'eternal existence' are identical states of affairs.

TP theorists appear to conflate the philosophical notion of eternal existence with the biblical reality of immortality and eternal life. They treat the believer's qualitatively distinct, "abundant" kind of spiritual life (John 10:10), referred to in the NT as "eternal life," as if it were both a necessary and sufficient condition for everlasting existence. This unwarranted assumption leads them to conclude that the damned cannot consciously exist forever. Craig (2018b) observes: "Until annihilationists grasp the fact that a person can exist forever and yet be spiritually dead, they will fundamentally misunderstand New Testament doctrine on immortality."

d. If TP is true, it would suggest that the nature of separation from God is metaphysical, thus resulting in the annihilation of the damned.

TP theorists also argue that the damned cannot continue to exist eternally due to their ultimate and irreversible separation from God, the source of all life.

However, they fail to recognize that this separation is not necessarily a *metaphysical contingency relation*; it can also consist in the loss of a *relational state of communion*, as Haratine and Smith (2023, p. 17) pointed out.

These TP advocates fail to distinguish between two senses of union:

1. *Metaphysical, contingency relation*: "If x is metaphysically contingent upon y , and disunion just means that x ceases to be contingent upon y , then x ceases to exist" (p. 17).

2. *Relational state of communion*: "Two individuals' wills align in support of at least one of the parties' flourishing" (p. 17).

Haratine and Smith (2023) clarify the purpose of this point:

We are only claiming that hell is disunion in this latter sense, and this is not logically equivalent to annihilation. As a result, we can be disunited with God in this way while still existing because we are still united with him in the former way. (pp. 17-18)

(a) If *retributive* TP is true, “the finite duration of sin” implies “a finite duration of punishment” (Burk, 2016, p. 87).

According to Stackhouse (2016), “Finite beings can perform only a finite amount of sin, and therefore a finite amount of suffering is sufficient to atone for it” (p. 87). However, as Burk (2016) points out, this argument “fails to recognize that the seriousness of sin—and thus of the punishment due to sin—is not measured by the duration of the sin [but] by the dignity of the one sinned against” (p. 87)⁷⁰.

(b) If *retributive* TP is true, it seems that the sacrifice of the God-man becomes unnecessary.

TP view, unlike the Anselmian *Cur Deus Homo* account, is incapable of explaining why God Himself needed to become human in order to save human FMAs from the penalty of Sin (type 1) and its everlasting consequences⁷¹. Furthermore, it seems that Stackhouse (2016) is primarily concerned with the need for the punishment of particular sins (type 2): “some therefore suffer worse than others since some sinned worse than others” (p. 78). However, he appears to completely avoid any discussion of the Sin (type 1) of rejecting God and/or Christ. I fail to see, therefore, how such Sin(s) could be paid for through *merely* temporary or finite punishments⁷².

⁷⁰ As a theologian, Burk (2016) rightly observes that Stackhouse’s statement is “without biblical warrant” (p. 87). Nowhere in Scripture are such declarations found. See also my earlier discussion regarding Stackhouse’s use of the term ‘*atone for*’ in relation to sin.

⁷¹ Although defenders of TP may understand ‘everlasting’ as implying a long-duration conscious torment that ultimately ends in annihilation, I maintain that the necessity of the God-man for atonement remains absolutely relevant due to Sin(s) (type 1), which are arguably of infinite gravity.

⁷² Frankly, I cannot even begin to imagine how a finite and sinful FMA could *atone* for such a grave evil. I believe that the offense of rejecting God (or His offer of salvation through His own sacrifice on the cross) is infinitely serious. How much *suffering* would it take to pay for something of such magnitude? If a TP advocate were to argue that even Sin (type 1) is a finite offense deserving only a finite punishment, I would consider *their* concept of God to be incomplete—and thus internally incoherent—due to its lack of great-making properties, particularly the ontologically necessary infinitude of the GPB.

4. *Universalist (CU)*:

a. **Theological Coherence.**

i. **Strengths:**

a. Universal salvation is the most emotionally desirable end. In fact, this human desire for universal salvation aligns with the will of God “who desires all people to be saved and to come to the knowledge of the truth” (1 Timothy 2:4, *ESV*, 2016).

b. Concerning atonement, as Parry (2016, p. 107) also observes, Scripture affirms that Christ Jesus “gave himself as a ransom for all,” that he “died for all”, that he “tasted death for everyone”, and that He Himself “is the propitiation for our sins, and not for ours only but also for the sins of the whole world” (1 Timothy 2:6; 2 Corinthians 5:14; Hebrews 2:9; 1 John 2:2, *ESV*, 2016). These texts, consistent with the broader witness of the NT, indicate that Christ’s self-sacrifice was of such high atoning and propitiatory⁷³ value that it *could* result in the actual redemption of all people.

c. There are several NT passages that *could* be interpreted as suggesting an ultimate CU salvation (see Romans 5:18; 11:32; 1 Corinthians 15:22; Philippians 2:11; Colossians 1:20).

d. In the books of the OT Prophets, we find numerous promises of restoration for Israel and other nations following a period of deserved punishment. This has led some proponents of CU to argue that such patterns legitimize the hope of an ultimate, universal restoration.

ii. **Weaknesses:**

a. Although universal salvation is the most emotionally desirable end—since, together with God, we would wish “all people to be saved and to come to the knowledge of the truth” (1 Timothy 2:4, *ESV*, 2016)—the fact is that the Bible never offers such hope to the damned.

b. The texts that could be interpreted as pointing to a CU ultimate salvation must be understood within the broader soteriological context of the NT, which clearly teaches that:

1. Salvation is found exclusively in Christ (John 8:24; 14:6; Acts 4:12; Romans 10:9–15; cf. 1 Corinthians 15:22 as for eschatological resurrection)

2. The opportunity for conversion is limited to this present earthly life (Hebrews 3:12–14, 9:27; 2 Corinthians 6:1–2; John 3:36)

⁷³ Atonement, in the context of Jesus’ sacrifice, refers to the offering by which sins are taken away. Propitiatory means that Christ’s sacrifice satisfies or appeases God’s holy wrath against all human sin, thereby establishing peace with God—both legally and relationally—for all who come to Him through faith in Jesus Christ.

3. A RP awaits those who depart this life without having turned to God (Hebrews 9:27; John 3:36; 5:29; Matthew 12:36; Romans 2:5–6; 8–9; 2 Thessalonians 1:6–10).

Since CU contradicts (2) and (3), CU cannot stand as consistent with NT teachings.

c. Appealing to these OT prophetic texts to support CU—especially the idea of post-hell salvation through Christ—commits at least three significant mistakes:

1. It reverses the proper hermeneutical order by interpreting the NT in light of the OT, rather than interpreting the OT in light of the theological fulfillment brought by the NT. The OT was *incomplete* apart from the New Covenant anticipated in Jeremiah 31 and fully inaugurated in the person and work of Christ.

2. It illegitimately moves from divine promises directed toward *nations*—concerning temporal *restoration* in *earthly* contexts—to conclusions about *individual*, eschatological *salvation* in a *heavenly* context. This constitutes a categorical shift that breaks analogy at multiple levels, particularly between national restoration and individual soteriology.

For instance, Parry (2016, p. 93) appeals to the restoration of “Sodom” mentioned in Ezekiel 16 as support for CU. However, this overlooks a crucial detail: Sodom was a city, not a collection of identifiable individuals from the past. The prophecy, thus, is not about the restoration of dead individuals, but about a city as a collective entity. There is no indication in the text that it refers to the post-mortem salvation of specific persons⁷⁴.

3. It overlooks the fact that *many* of the OT promises of restoration are addressed specifically to Israel—a people uniquely chosen by Yahweh for a particular covenantal purpose. Because of God’s covenantal faithfulness, he would not utterly forsake them. Their eventual restoration to the land promised to Abraham, following both punitive and restorative discipline, was not a universal principle but a covenantal fulfillment rooted in divine election.

⁷⁴ It is worth noting Sprinkle’s (2016) counterargument to Parry’s CU interpretation regarding the city of Sodom: “According to Parry’s view, the opportunity to repent and enter the door remains an everlasting option. But Jesus’s parable [*The Narrow Door*, in Luke 13:22–30] is quite clear that there will be a time when the door will be shut and never reopened” (p. 201).

b. Philosophical Implications.

i. Strengths:

a. If retributive CU is true, then punishment in hell appears to be both just and merciful: *just*, because evildoers are thought to be able to repay their debt to God; and *merciful*, because through serious, conscious punishment in hell, all evildoers will necessarily repent and be reconciled to God, thereby entering heaven on the legal basis of Christ's substitutionary sacrifice on the cross made on their behalf. Therefore, CU, at least *prima facie*, appears philosophically unobjectionable.

ii. Weaknesses:

a. If CU is true, PBT *does not make coherent sense*.

As with ISS and TP, CU also fails to fully appreciate divine perfection and the gravity of sin; therefore, my philosophical criticism (d) of ISS applies here in precisely the same way as well⁷⁵.

b. If *necessary* CU is true, it seems that God guarantees universal salvation through coercion.

Parry (2016) explains this *libertarian objection* as follows: "If people are *free*, God cannot *ensure* that they will accept the gospel. Consequently, unless God violates our freedom, he cannot *guarantee* that all will be saved" (p. 125).

Parry (2016) himself defends his CU hope (pp. 124-127) on the basis of arguments advanced by Thomas Talbott, who is the leading proponent of necessary universalism.

According to Walls (2013), who engaged extensively with Talbott's arguments over many years, Talbott asserts that hell is "*forcibly imposed punishment*" involving "*unbearable suffering*" which would eventually compel all FMAs to repent (p. 501). However, this claim contradicts Talbott's own defense of libertarian freedom, for such punishment and intense suffering would coerce all FMAs into repentance, thereby nullifying the possibility of a genuinely free choice (Walls, 2013, see pp. 505-506). Thus, Walls (2013) argues that Talbott faces a dilemma: "He must choose between his clarified account of divinely imposed misery and his claim that all sinners must inevitably arrive at a place where resistance to God is no longer possible." (pp. 505-506).

⁷⁵ Thus, see the philosophical implication (d) in the *Weaknesses* of ISS (pp. 44-45) where I explore this criticism.

He concludes that

this view of the pains of hell is at odds with his claim that God grants us the freedom to move ever further away from him. In order to maintain his case for necessary universalism, Talbott must choose the horn of the dilemma that involves embracing the sort of compulsion that he would prefer to repudiate. Otherwise, his case for necessary universalism fails. (Walls, 2013, p. 506)

- c. If CU is true, the incentive for pursuing righteousness during earthly life is significantly undermined.

While ECT and TP portray the final state of FMAs as an irreversible consequence of their Sin, CU maintains that all people will ultimately enter heaven, regardless of the actions they performed on earth. Although CU affirms the reality of conscious torment in hell, if Sinners come to accept CU as true—blinded by their love for sin—they may be inclined to risk continuing to live according to their own desires, deceiving themselves with an incomplete concept of God, i.e., a deity who, at the end of the day, cannot but forgive everything to everyone.

IV. Objections to ECT and Refutations

The following is a list of the most prominent objections to ECT, along with my responses in its defense.

A. Theological

1. *Semantic Limitation Objection:* The Greek term *aionios* may not support the traditional understanding of eternity in punishment.

Response:

Assuming that Jesus and the apostles intended to teach ECT, one must ask: What more could they have done linguistically to convey this in Greek? What specific terminology or additional lexical markers would one expect to find in the NT to communicate ECT unambiguously?

If the biblical authors had sought to assert TP, they could have employed explicit language denoting cessation of existence—avoiding the semantic ambiguity of *aionios*. Conversely, if they had wanted to communicate that after experiencing temporary conscious

torment, the damned might (or indeed would) eventually enter heaven, they could also have been more explicit and given a far clearer hope to that effect.

The NT's language appears sufficient to support ECT through a natural, intuitive reading. By contrast, to arrive just as naturally and intuitively at the alternative views such as TP and CU, one would reasonably expect less ambiguous language, less hyperbole, and—most of all—greater explicitness regarding the final state of the damned. Instead, we find language that *prima facie* suggests ECT (e.g., “unquenchable fire,” Mark 9:48).

What I mean is that, although defenders of alternative views sometimes offer interesting (CU)—and occasionally plausible (TP)—exegetical arguments in support of their interpretations, they overlook a crucial point: if Jesus and the apostles had intended to communicate the doctrine of ECT, they could hardly have used language more explicit than what we already find in the NT. Indeed, it seems that even if the NT writers had deliberately sought to teach ECT, proponents of alternative views would *still* feel exegetically justified in proposing alternative hermeneutical hypotheses. Yet, paradoxically, it also appears that the NT could not have articulated ECT any more clearly than it already does.

Thus, arguing for alternative views with any degree of confidence would require:

- (a) the use of far more explicit language and vocabulary in favor of those views, and
- (b) the avoidance of statements that naturally lead the reader in a different direction.

In contrast, I find that the language of Scripture is sufficiently clear for the doctrine of ECT to be intuitively grasped by the ordinary reader. Therefore, I regard the evidential basis for alternative views as insufficient—certainly not compelling.

In my judgment, ECT remains the best explanation for the full range of NT texts concerning the eschatological punishment of the damned. What ultimately concerns me is that, in teaching alternative views of hell as truth, churches may be listening more to theological speculation—however intellectually stimulating—than to the voice of Jesus, who, if He intended to teach ECT, could scarcely have done so more clearly.

2. Restorative Divine Character Objection: God's character as healer and restorer is inconsistent with everlasting punitive wrath.

Response:

First of all, the idea of God's restorative and healing character is clearly evident throughout the Bible, beginning with Genesis 3:15, where God promises that a descendant of the woman will ultimately defeat the serpent—that is, the devil (cf. Revelation 12). However, the promises of restoration for humankind find their fulfillment in the once-for-all, substitutionary death of Jesus, the God-man, on the cross (Hebrews 2:14–15; 9:26–28), so “that whoever believes in him should not perish but have eternal life” (John 3:16, *ESV*, 2016). For:

Whoever believes in him is not condemned, but whoever does not believe is condemned already, because he has not believed in the name of the only Son of God. And this is the judgment: the light has come into the world, and people loved the darkness rather than the light because their works were evil. For everyone who does wicked things hates the light and does not come to the light, lest his works should be exposed. (John 3:18-19, *ESV*, 2016).

The God-man had to undergo RP for humanity's sake, serving as humanity's legal proxy. This act is known as *Penal Substitution*, whereby “God inflicted upon Christ the suffering which we deserved as the punishment for our sins, as a result of which we no longer deserve punishment” (Craig, 2018a, p. 232). Accordingly, “God afflicted Christ with the suffering which, had it been inflicted upon us, would have been our just desert and, hence, punishment” (p. 232).

Therefore, far from contradicting God's restorative character, Scripture presents everlasting punitive wrath (Revelation 14:10–11; Matthew 25:41; Romans 2:5; 5:9) as precisely the kind of judgment the God-man had to endure on behalf of all (cf. Isaiah 53:5; 1 Peter 2:24; Romans 5:8), in order that believers might be reconciled to God.

This reconciliation, however, must occur through repentance and faith in the gospel during earthly life (Mark 1:14–15; Hebrews 3:12–14; 9:27; 2 Corinthians 6:1–2; John 3:36). After death, Scripture not only offers no hope of escape from hell, but explicitly affirms that death is followed by irreversible, everlasting judgment (Hebrews 9:27; John 3:36; 5:29; Matthew 12:36; 25:46; Romans 2:5–6, 8–9; 2 Thessalonians 1:6–10).

Thus, both the healing and restorative character of God and His punitive justice are fully manifested in the cross of Christ. At Calvary, divine mercy and justice meet. Because God loves

humanity and desires to restore it to a saving relationship with Himself, He, by grace and mercy, becomes incarnate, lives a sinless and exemplary life, and dies on a cross—experiencing there the very abandonment that sinners must undergo forever in hell (Mark 15:34; Matthew 27:46; cf. Psalm 22:1; Luke 13:28; 2 Thessalonians 1:8–9)—in order to pay the penalty for human sin (Romans 6:23; Mark 10:45; 1 Timothy 2:6).

Secondly, numerous promises of restoration appear throughout the prophetic literature of the OT. However, these promises primarily concern the people of Israel, who are assured a return to their land after a period of exile in a foreign nation. This exile is portrayed as a disciplinary and restorative punishment, inflicted by God so that, once the people acknowledge their wrongdoing and repent of their wickedness, they may return to their land and live in peace and blessing, walking in obedience to His law (the *Torah*).

Moreover, Israel possesses a unique set of divine promises that God has committed to fulfill throughout history—promises in which God Himself is the guarantor of their preservation, in order to bring His covenantal purposes to completion. Therefore, appeals to the restorative promises made to Israel, or to the ways God historically restored them, do not constitute a valid basis for asserting a universal restorative pattern in God's dealings with all humanity.

This is because God's relationship with Israel is fundamentally covenantal. It illustrates how God relates to a specific people with whom He has entered into a covenant or made specific promises—not how He relates to all of humanity irrespective of belief or covenantal standing, whether in this life or the next. To move from God's faithfulness to His covenant people to a universal claim about His restorative intentions toward the ungodly—who are neither Israel nor the Church—is a hermeneutically unjustified leap.

Finally, philosophically, I have tried to show in my main argument for ECT (pp. 24-27) that the existence of the GBP implies the truth of ECT—at least insofar as unrepentant Sinners exist.

3. *Conditional Immortality Objection:* Immortality—understood as both resurrection to everlasting life and enduring spiritual existence—is a gift granted exclusively to believers in Christ; the wicked, after undergoing their deserved punishment, will ultimately cease to exist—will be annihilated.

Response:

As indicated above (p. 50), a clear distinction must be made between *eternal life*—spiritual life in communion with God, described as ‘abundant’ (John 10:10) because of its qualitative nature, imparted by the Holy Spirit to the believer at the moment of conversion in this life—and *eternal existence*, which refers to mere conscious survival or persistence in a ruined state, spiritual first, and physical after eschatological resurrection.

Immortality, in the biblical sense, must be understood in the context of a *spiritual* or *heavenly* body (1 Corinthians 15), which God grants to believers so that they may dwell eternally in His presence. Thus, the believer will receive an *immortal* resurrection body, united to a spirit that partakes of God’s life—what Scripture calls ‘eternal life’ already since the day of their conversion to Christ through faith (John 3:16, 36; 6:47; Romans 6:23).

By contrast, the wicked, who *never had* eternal life (i.e., because they did not receive the Holy Spirit during their lifetime), will also be resurrected (John 5:29; Acts 24:15; Revelation 20:5, 12) but with bodies suited for eternal punishment. As Burk (2016) comments about Matthew 25:31–46, “the bodies that are cast into the fire have properties that make them fit for an eternal destiny” (pp. 29-30).

4. Temporal Cross Punishment Objection: A temporal atonement made by Christ is inconsistent with everlasting punishment for sinners.

Response:

The reason Christ did not need to undergo temporally unending suffering for the redemption of the FMAs is due to the infinite value of His Person. If He—whose value infinitely surpasses all things taken at once—receives, in human form (to be the proxy for these FMAs), the punishment the human FMAs deserve, the debt is fully paid, and God’s retributive justice fully satisfied, once and for all. As James White pointed out on *Unbelievable?* (Brierly, 2009), Christ’s identity as the “God-man” enabled His six-hour sacrifice to “propitiate the wrath of God” for believers of all times. It is “the nature of the Person suffering—not the duration”—that determines the atonement’s efficacy (37:10-38:30, as adapted by the author). Peterson (in E. Fudge & Peterson, 2000) also made this theological point:

In other words, because of the infinite dignity of Christ’s person, his sufferings, though finite in duration, were of infinite weight on the scales of divine justice (much as his righteousness, though displayed during his incarnation over a finite period, is of infinite weight). As God incarnate, Jesus

was capable of suffering in six hours on the cross what we can suffer only over an infinite period of time. (chapter 9)

B. Logical

1. Hell, as Evil vs God Objection: Hell's eternal evil conflicts with God's perfect goodness⁷⁶.

Response:

By counterposing evil with God's goodness, this objection seems to assume that (1) ECT is a moral evil. And hence: (a) God could not have morally sufficient reasons to allow it eternally; and (b) God could not inflict it, for He is perfect in goodness.

It is clear that, if either (1a) or (1b) were the case, then ECT would indeed be incompatible with PBT.

But what reasons are there for accepting (1) in the first place? If ECT, as conceived by traditionalism, is the result of justice (and even of a RJ), a virtue conceived as a great-making property in PBT, then the objection dissolves—since hell would be a moral good, existing to punish moral evil, especially the rejection of the Good in person as Lord of one's life, reestablishing thereby His moral order in the universe.

2. Divine Hiddenness Objection: ECT seems unjustified if God remains hidden to many people.

Response:

This objection assumes that God is truly hidden from some (or many) human beings. If that *were* the case, and those groups knew nothing about God at all, then ECT *would* indeed seem morally unjustified.

Nevertheless, the biblical testimony in favor of a general divine self-revelation to all mankind—in nature (Romans 1:18–23) and in conscience (Romans 2:14:15)—seems to be clear. Moreover, it is not only the Scriptural testimony. We also observe signs of an *apparent teleology* in creation. For my case, it is not necessary to argue that such an appearance corresponds to the reality of an intelligent design. It would suffice to acknowledge that creation *appears* to be

⁷⁶ This is a version of the *logical problem of evil*.

designed. Such “appearance of design” is what is supposed to point to the Creator and Designer of all things, so that the human beings who resist seeking that *apparent* Creator and wanting to submit to Him the control of their life as absolute Lord incurs an infinite demerit.

Likewise, we find in our conscience a kind of moral compass, which points to certain values that we must uphold and moral duties that we must fulfill. This is known as *Natural Law* in the work of Thomas Aquinas. We intuitively know that we must “do good and avoid evil” (Celano, 2006)⁷⁷. The existence of objective moral standards, however, points to a moral Lawgiver. That is what we call God.

Thus, to ignore the dictates of our moral conscience (provided it functions properly) in order to pursue personal preferences not aligned with the principle of Natural Law is to sin against the moral light that was given to us to guide us—even if we had no special divine revelation (i.e., the Bible).

As the apostle Paul claims:

For all who have sinned without the law will also perish without the law, and all who have sinned under the law will be judged by the law. ...

For when Gentiles, who do not have the law, by nature do what the law requires, they are a law to themselves, even though they do not have the law. They show that the work of the law is written on their hearts, while their conscience also bears witness, and their conflicting thoughts accuse or even excuse them ... (Romans 2:12, 14–15, *ESV*, 2016)

A short formulation of John Shellenberg’s argument from Divine Hiddenness⁷⁸ would be as follows:

1. “If God exists, there are no nonresistant nonbelievers.
2. There are nonresistant nonbelievers.
3. God does not exist.” (Philosophy at the University of Edinburgh, 2017)

I would contend, however, that:

⁷⁷ *Summa Theologica* I-II, 94, 2 (cited in Celano, 2006).

⁷⁸ It would be pertinent, at this point, to include a broader analysis of John Schellenberg’s argument from Divine Hiddenness, but such an analysis would be beyond the scope of this paper. Therefore, I will limit myself to offering a few brief responses to this argument.

(a) As for (1), God’s goal is not *merely* that people *know* He exists, but that they *enter* into a saving love relationship with Him.

(b) As for (2), the idea that there are nonresistant nonbelievers to such kind of personal relationship with God is very speculative—it cannot be demonstrated.

(c) The objector would have to demonstrate that God could, by revealing Himself more clearly, draw more people into such a personal saving love relationship.

(ReasonableFaithOrg, 2017, 41:53-43:53)

(d) Molinism, which I hold to, provides a twofold answer to the issue of divine hiddenness: First, it is *possible* that, *sans* creation, God—through His middle knowledge—knew who would freely (in the libertarian sense) accept and who would freely reject His offer of salvation in Christ in all FW, and has chosen to actualize that world in which the greatest number of people could be freely saved through Christ (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapters 28, 33). Second, it is *possible* that God has so ordered the world that those who never hear the gospel are precisely those whom He knew would freely reject His offer of salvation, had they heard it (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34).

Thus, if divine hiddenness cannot be demonstrated—specifically, that there are large groups of individuals who are entirely unaware of God’s existence—then it is rational to conclude that there do not appear to be individuals who, had they known slightly more about God, would have responded positively to His offer of salvation in Christ.

3. PBT Incompatibility Objection: ECT does not fit well with PBT because an all-powerful and all-loving being would be able to bring about the universal salvation that He wills⁷⁹.

⁷⁹ A different way of formulating the same objection would be: “An omnipotent God could create a world in which all moral agents freely choose life with God” (Baker, 2015, p. 6). In that case, a more appropriate name would be Possible World Objection. Ray Bradley (in Craig & Bradley, 1994) used just this objection in his debate with Craig. He characterized, however, heaven as a PW which the omnipotent God could actualize. To this, Craig replied during the time of cross-examination that Bradley was wrong: “heaven isn’t a possible world. A PW “is a maximal state of affairs--which includes not just the afterlife, but the pre-life on the way to heaven. And the point is here that ... it may not be *feasible* for God to actualize heaven in isolation from such an antecedent world” (Craig & Bradley, 1994, *my emphasis*). As Craig explains:

Heaven may not be a possible world when you take it in isolation by itself. It may be that the only way in which God could actualize a heaven of free creatures all worshipping Him and not falling into sin would be by having, so to speak, this run-up to it, this advance life during which there is a veil of decision-making in which some people choose for God and some people against God. Otherwise you don’t know that heaven is an actualizable world. You have no way of knowing that possibility. (Craig & Bradley, 1994)

Response:

It is true that God is able to bring this universal salvation about, but it may be the case that a universal salvation could only come about at the expense of LFW—a good that God values as a necessary condition for the establishment of a genuine love relationship between creatures and the Creator. Thus, if the cost of such a universal salvation is to deprive FMAs of the precious good of LFW, a presumably necessary component of being *Imago Dei*, and if the divine objective in creating human FMAs was that they might freely relate to Him (just as the Trinity enjoys eternally intra-trinitarian love), such a universal salvation would completely frustrate His primary relational purpose between Him and His people—a theme that is constantly repeated as a refrain throughout Scripture: “He will dwell with them, and they will be his people” (Revelation 21:3; *ESV*, 2016; cf. Ezekiel 37:27, Jeremiah 31:33, 2 Corinthians 6:16, Leviticus 26:11–12, Zechariah 8:8, Hebrews 8:10; John 1:14; 14:23). Thus, since humans were created by God to enjoy everlastingly a loving relationship with the GPB, but not all choose to participate in it, it might be the case that there are no FWs in which both circumstances—(a) a universal salvation and (b) a salvation of free creatures (FMAs)—occur. Moreover, there is an additional condition that is to be taken into account, i.e., an optimal balance between the saved and the lost:

As a good and loving God, God wants as many people as possible to be saved and as few as possible to be lost. His goal, then, is to achieve an optimal balance between these, where optimality involves not just absolute numbers but also the ratio between saved and lost. Among those worlds known via His middle knowledge to be feasible for Him to create, God restricts His creative choice to that subset of worlds in which an optimal balance between saved and lost obtains, and chooses to create one of these worlds. But then, it is possible that the actual world (which includes the future as well as the present and past) has such a balance. It is possible that in order to create this many people who will be saved, God also had to create this many people who will be lost. It is possible that had God created a world in which fewer people go to hell, then even fewer people would have gone to heaven. It is possible that in order to achieve a multitude of saints, God had to accept a multitude of sinners. (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34)

Therefore, considering God's three desires—(a) universal salvation, (b) salvation of free creatures, and (c) optimal balance (because God does not want a world of *free* and *universal* salvation with very few inhabitants, where, e.g., only “two or three people” are saved, but where if one more were to be added, he/she would be lost, (drcraigvideos, 2012, 1:50-:2:00))—it is possible that (b) and (c) are *trans-worldly incompatible* (or non-compostable) with (a).

C. Moral

1. *Love-based objections*

a. Foreknown Damnation Objection. “An omnibenevolent God would not create a world with the foreknowledge that some (perhaps a significant proportion) of God's creatures would end up in hell” (Baker, 2015, p. 6).

Response:

I find Craig's response to this objection compelling and totally representative of my own view:

Possible answer: God wanted to share his love and fellowship with created persons. He knew this meant that many would freely reject him and be lost. But he also knew that many others would freely receive his grace and be saved. The happiness and blessedness of those who would freely embrace his love should not be precluded by those who would freely spurn him. Persons who would freely reject God and his love should not be allowed, in effect, to hold a sort of veto power over which worlds God is free to create. In his mercy God has providentially ordered the world to achieve an optimal balance between saved and lost by maximizing the number of those who freely accept him and minimizing the number of those who would not. (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34)

That is why I fully concur with Craig that so long as God gives sufficient grace for salvation to all persons he creates, God seems no less loving for preferring a more populous world, even though that implies that some people would freely resist his every effort to save them and be damned. (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34)

In conclusion, God’s foreknowledge of the fact that some of His creatures will end up in hell does not constitute a normative reason not to create such a world, insofar as (a) the ultimate fate of the damned is a consequence of their free (LFW) rejection of God’s sufficient grace for salvation, and (b) God, in His mercy, has providentially ordered creation to maximize “the number of those who freely accept Him” while minimizing the number of those who would not—thus achieving an “optimal balance between saved and lost” (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34).

b. Saints’ Joy Objection⁸⁰. It is implausible that the redeemed could experience perfect joy in heaven while being eternally aware that their loved ones are suffering unending torment.

Response:

I find the most plausible response to this objection to be the one articulated by Walls (2013):

The saved will see the nature of evil with such perfect moral clarity that they will not be disturbed by the reality of damnation. They will clearly understand the damned have freely chosen their fate, and if they will not repent, they cannot be allowed to hold heaven hostage. The damned can refuse to accept God’s invitation to joy but they cannot have the right or power to spoil the happiness of those who have accepted the invitation simply because they will not. (p. 507)

This answer, in fact, is supported by Scripture. As Burk (2016) rightly points out, the book of Revelation (18:20; 19:3) teaches that the reality of eternal damnation “will ultimately become a source of joy and praise for the saints as they witness the infinite goodness and justice of God” (p. 20). The first text (Revelation 18:20, see the context) speaks of God’s vengeance or judgment on the “city” that persecuted and martyred the Christians, which becomes a cause for rejoicing in heaven, as God has at last executed justice on their behalf. The second text, in the same vein, offers praise to God for the fact that “the smoke from her goes up forever and ever” (Revelation 19:3, *ESV*, 2016; for more support see 19:1–5).

⁸⁰ Strictly speaking, this is an objection to the doctrine of heaven—the counterpart to the traditional doctrine of hell (ECT). Nonetheless, since both doctrines concern interconnected and irreversible eschatological destinies, I find it relevant to address this objection here.

c. Postmortem Mercy Objection. If God is maximally loving and just, He would extend genuine postmortem opportunities for repentance and union with Him—especially for those misled, uninformed, or hardened by trauma in life.

Response:

This objection appears to assume that LFW persists in hell. Although I do not endorse this view, I believe it raises a philosophical challenge that merits a response.

First, even if it were true that the damned are not deprived of LFW during their punishment in hell, I believe the objector overlooks the fact that a maximally—or optimally—loving God would have already given the damned sufficient grace during their earthly lives to ensure—or guarantee—that if, under more favorable earthly circumstances—where divine *common grace* was manifested in their everyday lives—they did not want to convert to Him, that much less will they do so under the circumstances of their RP, where divine common grace will no longer be experienced. For the One who “makes His sun rise on the evil and on the good, and sends rain on the just and on the unjust” (Matthew 5:45, *ESV*, 2016) will, in hell, have already withdrawn those generous benefits that the damned used to enjoy undeservedly on earth.

When a person persistently renounces, until the day of their death, the government of God over their life (Sin type 1)—refusing to seek the Maker of the universe, whose imprint they must necessarily have perceived, *at least*, in nature and conscience during the time of grace given to them to decide whether they desire to know and be eternally with God—that person effectively chooses a permanent destiny apart from Him.

Thus, it is misguided to object to ECT on the grounds of divine love and justice by demanding postmortem opportunities, since for a wise, gracious, and omniscient being, such opportunities are not necessary to ensure a fair and just judgment⁸¹.

Secondly, regarding the aforementioned individuals who were misled, uninformed, or trauma-hardened in life, it is first necessary to ask whether they perceived enough of God’s testimony through creation and conscience (at the very least) to allow for a fair judgment of their case. Since the general knowledge of God through general revelation is axiomatic in the NT (see Romans 1:18–23; cf. Psalm 19; Acts 14:17), it seems unreasonable to posit a postmortem opportunity in light of this clear apostolic teaching.

⁸¹ See also my response below to the Non-Restoration Objection, which provides a fuller picture of my treatment of the issue of postmortem opportunities.

As for those specifically hardened by trauma, although they share in the witness of general revelation, it is reasonable to postulate that the GPB *would be* responsible for addressing their trauma during their lifetime—*ensuring* that they are not condemned *due to* a wounded state for which they are not morally accountable.

Thus, I see no compelling reason to affirm the necessity of postmortem opportunities under the framework of PBT.

d. Value Account of Love Objection. ECT diverges from two of the three values of love: it fails to satisfy the flourishing and friendship values⁸².

Response:

According to Jordan Wessling’s Value Account of Love, love consists in valuing (1) the existence, (2) the flourishing, and (3) the friendship of a person (Mullins, 2022, p. 3, Helda electronic reprint). If ECT contradicts Wessling’s (2020) Value Account of Love, it is not because ECT is inconsistent with PBT, but because it conflicts with what Wessling (2021) called “The Identity Thesis” (p. 148)—the claim that “‘God’s love is identical to His moral goodness,’ such that ‘God possesses no moral attribute that is not essentially and most fundamentally a matter of love.’” (Craig, 2025, p. 453). As I have already argued⁸³, there are strong theological reasons to reject this thesis. I affirm, instead, a balanced view of the divine attributes, in which both, divine justice and love, are “equally essential to God and therefore uncompromisable” within a PBT framework⁸⁴ (ReasonableFaithOrg, 2024, 21:07-21:14, as transcribed and adapted by the author).

While I accept Wessling’s values of love as genuine qualities of divine love, I maintain that God’s justice and holiness demand the punishment of Sinners—a punishment proportional to the worth of the One against whom FMAs have Sinned. Thus, although the GPB values FMA

⁸² Mullins (2022), who critically analyzes views on hell using two criteria—(1) Wessling’s (2020) value account of love (i.e., valuing (a) existence, (b) flourishing, and (c) friendship) and (2) the biblical *ultimate defeat of evil*—finds that while ECT satisfies (1a), it diverges from (1b) and (1c). Wessling, on the other hand, would reject a version of hell where the damned “can no longer sin in hell” and “can do nothing but bear their just punishment for all eternity” (p. 5, Helda electronic reprint). Mullins (2022) therefore concludes: “the traditional doctrine of hell should be rejected. So we need to look elsewhere to see how God can ultimately defeat evil without diverging from love (p. 5, Helda electronic reprint).

⁸³ See point (a) under the philosophical weaknesses of ISS in Section C.

⁸⁴ Craig rightly notes in his dialogue with Wessling (ReasonableFaithOrg, 2024) that both love and justice are essential aspects of God’s moral perfection and should be viewed as equal rather than hierarchical. He contends, “if it’s philosophically coherent to affirm the equal weight of both justice and love within the divine character, then I think we should do so” (33:53-34:04, as transcribed by the author).

flourishing and desires eternal friendship with them, He must uphold justice and restore moral order by giving Sinners their due.

Accordingly, there is no contradiction between the two love-related values in Wessling's account and my compatibilist version of ECT, because my concept of the GPB rejects the Identity Thesis and affirms a balanced view of divine attributes. God's goodness—referred to in Scripture as His righteousness—entails both love and justice in equal measure. Indeed, any imbalance among God's attributes would compromise the very notion of divine perfection. A God who eternally prioritizes mercy over justice, e.g., would be morally compromised—weak, partial, and ultimately manipulable. Such a being could not be the greatest conceivable being and therefore would not qualify as a BWW.

2. *Justice-based objections*

a. Proportionality Objection. ECT entails a totally disproportionate punishment to finite sins⁸⁵.

Response:

ECT advocates agree with the objectors on the proportionality principle, according to which “the punishment must fit the crime” (Crisp, 2003, p. 37). It is precisely this principle, nonetheless, that leads the traditionalist to view ECT punishment as unavoidable—if Sin (type 1), performed by an FMA, exists. In my view, in all PWs where both GPB and Sin exist, ECT punishment must necessarily exist. I affirm what Crisp (2003) refers to as “the *strong divine justice claim*” (p. 37), which holds that “divine justice *does not permit forgiveness*” (p. 36) “without retributive justice being served” (p. 37)—i.e., without the sacrificial death of the God-man on behalf of FMAs to satisfy the demands of God's infinite justice.

Crisp (2003) articulates the rationale behind this view:

God is infinitely great in glory and honour, such that every sin against God is infinitely serious (quite apart from its consequences). Nevertheless, there are infinite consequences because all sin against this God incurs an infinite demerit, since it is an affront to the infinite glory and honour of God, thereby accruing an infinite disvalue. (p. 37)

⁸⁵ Stackhouse (2016), e.g., asserts that: “Finite beings can perform only a finite amount of sin, and therefore a finite amount of suffering is sufficient to atone for it” (p. 79).

While, according to Crisp (2003), Talbott—the chief CU critic of ECT—argues that any crime, “however severe, can never incur an everlasting punishment, since this violates the principle of proportionality”⁸⁶ (p. 39), Crisp contends that Talbott’s “response fails to take into consideration” that “for any person who commits a sin, the guilt accruing for that sin leading to punishment is proportional” not only to “(a) the severity of the actual or intended harm to the person or object concerned,” but also to “(b) the kind of being against whom the wrong is committed” (p. 39). As Crisp (2003) explains, “The value of a deity outweighs the value of a human to an infinite degree, such that crimes against a member of that ontological kind carry significantly greater (in fact, infinite) consequences” (p. 40). Thus, Crisp’s (2003) argument for infinite punishment would be as follows:

- (1) God is infinitely worthy of regard.
- (2) The gravity of an offence against a being is principally determined by its worth or dignity.
- (3) There is an infinite demerit in all sin⁸⁷ against God.
- (4) Hence, all sin is infinitely heinous. (p. 41).

The objection posed by William Wainwright to (4)—i.e., that “a sin may incur an infinite demerit, and thereby be infinitely heinous, but not warrant an infinite punishment” (p. 41), because, as Crisp (2003) explains, “a person may commit a crime without full knowledge of it being a crime, or inadvertently, or not wholly willingly” (p. 41)—does not affect my case for ECT, since my case rests solely on the basis of Sin (type 1), defined in this work as:

the rejection of God as Lord over a person’s life through

⁸⁶ Swinburne (1983), who is an advocate of ISS, in contrast to Talbott, criticizes only the *physical* aspect of ECT as disproportional (though by *sin* he seems to mean only what I call sin(s) (type 2)):

But for God to subject them to literally endless physical pain (*poena sensus* in medieval terminology) does seem to me to be incompatible with the goodness of God. It seems to have the character of a barbarous vengeance; whatever the evil, a finite number of years of evildoing does not deserve an infinite number of years of physical pain as punishment. The all-important punishment is to be deprived of eternal happiness (this is the *poena damni* in medieval terminology). (pp. 51-52)

⁸⁷ I remain agnostic as to whether sin(s) (type 2) accrue infinite demerit in the same way as Sin (type 1).

- (a) the desire for independence from God, seeking autonomy in the moral sphere instead of submission to His will, or
- (b) the rejection of the Gospel of Jesus Christ, whereby a person refuses to place their trust in Him for salvation from the penalty of Sin and its everlasting consequences. (p. 15)

Lastly, recall my main defense of ECT (see pp. 24-27, *Why ECT?*), as it serves here to counter the Proportionality Objection: “If, however, FMAs fall—i.e., become disobedient to His will—they incur a kind of debt that, due to the ontological greatness of the GPB—i.e., His qualitative infinity (QI)—would be *metaphysically impossible* for them *to repay*.” Therefore, not only is ECT not disproportionate, but it is also deeply interconnected with the concept of God as the GPB.

b. Evil Persistence Objection. If people sin everlastingly in hell, evil will never be defeated.

Response:

First, according to the Bible, the defeat of evil does not consist in its disappearance from existence but in its everlasting punishment. The wicked will be everlastingly separated from God and His people, confined to the “lake of fire and sulfur” (Revelation 21:8; cf. 20:14, *ESV*, 2016), where they will be tormented forever. Deprived of any ability to enter the presence of God and His people (see Revelation 21:27), they will pose no threat to the eternal peace and joy of the redeemed.

Secondly, e.g., Craig—in his debate with Ray Bradley (1994)—offers, apart from the thesis of what I call Sin (type 1) which “deserves infinite punishment”, a plausible alternative explanation for why the punishment of hell may be infinite in duration: i.e., the hypothesis that the damned continue to sin *a parte post*, thereby accruing “more guilt” and thus “more punishment” (Craig & Bradley, 1994) presumably being endowed with LFW even in hell.

It is this view of everlasting sinning in hell what Mullins (2022) criticizes: “If God lets the damned carry on sinning forever in hell, then God will not ultimately defeat evil” (p. 5, Helda electronic reprint). As I have expressed so far, I do not see that the Bible requires the extinction of evil from the physical (or metaphysical) universe in order to affirm the ultimate defeat of evil. Nevertheless, for the sake of argument, I would concede that if one adopts a view according to which the ultimate defeat of evil demands its complete extinction from the universe, then under that LFW approach to hell, evil would indeed continue to exist forever in some form—even if it can never harm any inhabitant of heaven. In that case, I would agree with Mullins on this point.

Lastly, in contrast to the approach proposed by Craig above, I affirm what Mullins (2022) calls “a traditional doctrine of hell,” wherein “the damned can no longer sin. Their fate is sealed, and they are no longer able to rebel or repent. They can do nothing but bear their just punishment for all of eternity” (p. 5, Helda electronic reprint). Therefore, under the ECT view I defend, the Evil Persistence Objection is dissolved. The inhabitants of hell retain only a *compatibilist* kind of free will: they choose what they desire, but their desires are entirely determined by their (fallen) nature. In this view, they remain individuals, but no longer function as FMAs. As such, they no longer bear moral responsibility before God for their actions, since they are incapable of choosing anything other than what their strongest fallen desires dictate. They preserve self-awareness, awareness of the environment and of the past (the memories of their earthly choices). Although they *seem* eternally rebellious given their *apparent* God-hating behavior, in reality *they are not*. Their reactions to the punishment they justly experience for their evil earthly choices are understandable, but these do not constitute sin (or rebellion) because hell inhabitants lack LFW.

c. Epistemic Disparity Objection. Unequal access to spiritual knowledge (i.e., to knowledge or understanding about God, the Bible, the gospel of Jesus Christ) raises fairness concerns about *identical* ECT outcomes.

Response:

As already established in (see pp. 21-22; 28), Scripture affirms degrees of punishment that are proportional to the degree of light rejected by FMAs. Thus, ECT outcomes will not be identical for all hell inhabitants.

Furthermore, Crisp (2003) anticipates this objection by arguing that the Infinite Punishment Thesis (IPT) does not entail the Equal Punishment Thesis (EPT). He illustrates this point as follows:

But if the IPT obtains, then does this entail that all sinners are punished equally as well as infinitely? No, it does not. Let us say that there are two sinners, Trevor and Gary. Both are consigned to hell forever. Both suffer an infinite punishment in hell. But Trevor is only punished for one hour a day whereas Gary is punished for twelve hours a day⁸⁸. Clearly, in

⁸⁸ One might rightly wonder how the analogy of punishment by hours in a day translates into a state of permanent separation from God. Several factors must be considered here: What theory of time should we embrace for the afterlife? Does the concept of space even apply in hell? Do the damned possess bodies of some kind? Personally, I uphold the Tensed Theory of Time (A-theory of time). I therefore believe that physical time begins to count from the

this state of affairs they are both punished infinitely but not equally. Therefore, an IPT does not entail an Equal Punishment Thesis (EPT). The two issues are distinct. This is important since it is often claimed that if God punishes two people infinitely for two different orders of sin (one venial, say, the other mortal), then this is unjust. But of course, God may punish two people infinitely, but not equally. It may be that there is a threshold of punishment for all sin which is infinite, but that different sins are treated differently for the purposes of the severity of the punishment endured. (There is some Scriptural support for such a view, the classic example of which is the parable of the Talents in Matthew 25:14–30.)

Even if the infinite punishment endured is unremitting, such that Trevor and Gary both experience their punishment without relief, this does not entail an EPT, since unremitting punishments may still admit differing degrees of punishment. For instance, unremitting pain from a headache is not as severe as the unremitting pain of having a bilateral leg amputation. Both may be unremittingly painful, though not equally unremittingly painful (p. 38).

d. Non-Restoration Objection. Everlasting punishment with no possibility of repentance is unjust.

Response:

First of all, what is truly *just* is, it seems to me, that the Sinners who passed into eternity without having repented—despite all of God’s loving efforts to bring them to repentance while there was still time—should spend eternity suffering “the punishment of eternal destruction, away from the presence of the Lord and from the glory of his might” (2 Thessalonians 1:9, *ESV*, 2016). The rejection of the Perfect Being (Sin type 1), in any of its forms, as long as it is exercised through

creation of the universe. At *this very moment*, neither what we remember as the “past” exists, nor has the future yet come into being—only a becoming called the “present,” which is experienced in real time and, since creation, continues *ad infinitum*. So, first, of the damned, it is said that “the smoke of their torment goes up forever and ever, and they have no rest, day or night” (Revelation 14:11, *ESV*, 2016), which, at least literally, suggests the passing of days much like those we experience in our lives. Even if the reference is metaphorical, we know that metaphors bear some meaningful analogy to the imagery they employ. Thus, although all the damned must suffer punishment for their Sin (type 1) constantly and perpetually, I agree with Crisp in maintaining that this does not imply there cannot be *relief* in the experience of punishment for sins (type 2), nor that there are no degrees in the intensity of suffering experienced in hell. Secondly, the imagery provided in Scripture suggests that hell is a place, and therefore appears to be spatial. Third, Scripture clearly indicates that not only the saints but also the damned will possess resurrection bodies, with which they will pass into their eternal destinations. All in all, it appears that both the damned and the saints will continue to experience the passage of time within a spatial reality, with special resurrection bodies suited to their respective everlasting destinations.

the use of LFW and under the influence of God's *prevenient grace* (by which He convicts individuals of Sin, its consequences, and the necessity of turning to God/Christ for forgiveness), certainly merits everlasting retribution. For an infinitely heinous act has been committed against the only Being who is ontologically and eternally Worthy of Worship (BWW) and of the highest regard.

Even worse becomes the picture when we consider that this rejection of God was something the FMAs resolutely persisted in throughout their lives, until their very last breath. Such an attitude only aggravates their state of perdition, as the FMA had enjoyed countless benefits that God, in His love, continually bestowed upon them throughout their life—and yet, each time they were confronted with God's loving *prevenient grace*, they chose to reject it. As Scripture states in the OT:

Seek the Lord while he may be found; call upon him while he is near; let the wicked forsake his way, and the unrighteous man his thoughts; let him return to the Lord, that he may have compassion on him, and to our God, for he will abundantly pardon. (Isaiah 55:6–7, *ESV*, 2016)

Hell, therefore, is a RP—it is not about new opportunities but about receiving what is deserved, a penalty incalculable in view of the magnitude and heinousness of Sin.

Secondly, Craig, in his debate with Bradley (1994) observes that even if God permitted “the damned to leave hell and go to heaven,” it is *possible* that “they [would] freely refuse to do so.” He argues:

It is possible that persons in hell grow only more implacable in their hatred of God as time goes on. Rather than repent and ask God for forgiveness, they continue to curse Him and reject Him. God thus has no choice but to leave them where they are. In such a case, the door to hell is locked, as John Paul Sartre said, from the *inside*. The damned thus choose eternal separation from God. So, again, so as long as any of these scenarios is even possible, it invalidates the objection that God's perfect justice is incompatible with everlasting separation from God⁸⁹. (Craig & Bradley, 1994)

⁸⁹ Although this argument sounds like the ISS, this is primarily because, as Baker (2015) indicates, “William Lane Craig supplements his belief in eternal conscious torment with the Fixed Character Thesis and a molinist interpretation of divine omniscience (Craig 1989)” (p. 15).

Finally, everlasting punishment with no possibility of repentance could be also just, if, as Craig (1989) argues, *transworld damnation* were true:

it is possible that some persons would not freely receive Christ under any circumstances. Suppose, then, that God has so ordered the world that all persons who are actually lost are such persons. In such a case, anyone who actually is lost would have been lost in any world in which God had created him. It is possible, then, that although God, in order to bring this many persons to salvation, had to pay the price of seeing this many persons lost, nevertheless He has providentially ordered the world such that those who are lost are persons who would not have been saved in any world feasible for God in which they exist. On the analogy of transworld depravity⁹⁰, we may accordingly speak of the property of *transworld damnation*, which is possessed by any person who freely does not respond to God's grace and so is lost in every world feasible for God in which that person exists. (p. 184).

Therefore, if transworld damnation is true, then everlasting punishment with no possibility of repentance is undoubtedly just.

e. Unevangelized Acceptance Objection. It seems unjust for God not to bring the gospel to people who would have freely accepted it, even if they rejected the light of general revelation that they had.

Response:

I concur with Craig's Molinist approach in responding to this objection. God, through His *middle knowledge*, may have ordered the world in such a way that those who would respond positively to the gospel if they heard it, actually do hear it during their lifetime:

Possible answer: There are no such people. God in his providence has so arranged the world that those who would respond to the gospel if they heard it, do hear it. The sovereign God has so ordered human history that as the gospel spreads out from first-century Palestine, he places people in its path who would believe it if they heard it. Once the gospel reaches a people, God providentially places there persons whom he knew would respond to it if they heard it. In his love and mercy, God ensures that no one who would believe the

⁹⁰ Craig refers here to Alvin Plantinga's (1978) *The Nature of Necessity*, pp. 184-199.

gospel if he heard it is born at a time and place in history where he fails to hear it. Those who do not respond to God's general revelation in nature and conscience and never hear the gospel would not respond to it if they did hear it. Hence, no one is lost because of historical or geographical accident. Anyone who wants or even would want to be saved will be saved. (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34)

This possible answer is quite attractive because it seems to have biblical support in the discourse of Paul to the Athenians: "And [God] made from one man every nation of mankind to live on all the face of the earth, having determined allotted periods and the boundaries of their dwelling place" (Acts 17:26, *ESV*, 2016).

f. Vagueness Justice Objection. A binary afterlife (Heaven/Hell) cannot be just because any divine criterion based on vague or gradable factors (e.g., faith, morality) forces arbitrary cutoffs and, as a result, it violates proportional justice by treating nearly identical cases radically differently (Sider, 2002)⁹¹.

Response:

I would argue that the Protestant notion of legal or *forensic justification* addresses all of Sider's (2002) justice-related concerns. If salvation is based on entering into a personal, saving love-relationship with God through trust in Christ—where one is legally declared righteous by God—then salvation depends on a *binary* covenantal status, not on gradual spiritual states.

Thus, the righteousness of Jesus—imputed to the repentant believer (i.e., to the one who trusts in Jesus as their Lord and personal Savior)—results in a new, vibrant, and transformed spiritual life, called "eternal life" in the New Testament (Romans 4:5, 5:1; Titus 3:7; 2 Corinthians 5:21; Galatians 2:21). This new life, given by the Holy Spirit (John 3:6)—due to the ontological change that this regeneration involves—is characterized by an inner disposition to hate sin, on the

⁹¹ Buckareff and Plug (2013) summarize very well Sider's position:

The traditional conception of hell is committed to arbitrary cut-offs between the unsaved and the saved, and that the arbitrariness of the cut-offs is incompatible with God's perfect justice. It is incompatible due to the discrepancy in treatment between two extremely similar persons who happen to fall on either side of the cut-off. (p. 3; for a broader discussion, see also pp. 5-7).

one hand, and to love God, on the other (1 John 3:9–10). Therefore, while this legal notion eliminates problematic *cutoffs*, it simultaneously preserves divine justice.⁹²

V. My Defense: Compatibility of Divine Perfection and Everlasting Punishment

A. My View

As Walls (2013) rightly points out, “The ultimate destiny of every person is either eternal joy of unimaginable glory and delight or eternal misery of unspeakable horror” (p. 491).

1. Positively: Firstly, I consider ECT to be not only the theologically most consistent view with *Tota Scriptura*, but also—despite all objections examined so far—the philosophically least problematic and rationally most intuitive position in view of divine infinity, holiness, and justice. Thus, I see it as inevitable to conclude that Sinning against an *infinite* God must morally and metaphysically entail an *infinite* punishment, so that the punishment fits the crime.

Accordingly, if God (GPB) is holy and just, He can leave no sin unpunished—least of all the Sin of rejection of God⁹³. And if God is all-loving and merciful, then even before He created the world—a world in which there would be infinite evil, rebellion, and punishment for Sin—He would have already prepared redemption, by His own infinitely valuable (QI) Self-sacrifice, for all those men and women whom He knew would surrender the control of their lives to Him (Jesus) as their absolute Lord and King, acknowledging Him as their only Savior, as the One who made a sufficient atoning sacrifice for their eternal redemption.

Secondly, regarding my position on the problem of religious diversity in the world, I reject universalism—“the doctrine that every human being will partake of God’s salvation”—and hold

⁹² Another answer to the Vagueness Justice Objection has been given by Dougherty and Poston (2008). As Buckareff and Plug (2013) inform, Dougherty and Poston argue that “God would not actualize a world with borderline cases” (p. 6). They take a *skeptical theism* approach to respond to this issue.

⁹³ While finite sins (type 2) may warrant finite punishments, the foundational offense (Sin type 1) is the FMAs refusal to submit to God’s authority. Therefore, rejecting the GPB—the very standard of morality—is *infinitely* grave, deserving *infinite* consequences.

to *Christian particularism*—“the view that only some, but not all, human beings will partake of God’s salvation” (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34).

Within Christian particularism—in reference to the response that human beings must give to the light provided by God—I identify theologically with what Craig (in Moreland & Craig, 2017) calls *Christian restrictivism*—according to which “salvation is available only through an appropriate response to God’s special revelation concerning Christ, which requires a faith response to the message of the gospel of Christ” (chapter 34). Nonetheless, I recognize the *possibility* that *Christian accessibilism*—according to which “for those who have not had the benefit of special revelation, salvation is available through their appropriate response to God’s general revelation in nature and conscience” (chapter 34)—given God’s sovereignty, *might* be true. Thus, it is *possible* for some people—e.g., those unreached by the Gospel—to be justified (Romans 4:3) through a response of trusting faith (like Noah, Job and Abraham in the OT times) in the God they have known through general revelation—given in nature and moral conscience (Romans 1:18–23; 2:14–15).

As for the basis and means of salvation through Jesus Christ, I identify theologically more with *Christian exclusivism*—according to which “people actually appropriate God’s salvation only on the basis of Christ’s work and through explicit faith in him” (chapter 34)—because I see that God’s way of working in the last 2,000 years has included appearing—as Jesus—in dreams or visions⁹⁴ to people who He knew *would* believe in Him if they *had* knowledge of the Gospel, or sending an angel to communicate that the person in question has to meet with a Christian x, who will communicate to them the Gospel message that they need to hear in order to be saved (e.g., Acts 10). I recognize, however, the *possibility* that *Christian inclusivism*—according to which “people actually appropriate God’s salvation only on the basis of Christ’s work but not always through explicit faith in him” (chapter 34)—*might* be true, given God’s sovereignty (just as I acknowledge the possibility of Christian accessibilism). Accordingly, it is *possible* for not only

⁹⁴ See the following works in support of this claim: Garrison, D. (2014). *A wind in the house of Islam: How God is drawing Muslims around the world to faith in Jesus Christ*. WIGTake Resources; Richardson, D. (1981). *Eternity in their hearts* (Rev. ed.). Regal Books; Doyle, T. (2012). *Dreams and visions: Is Jesus awakening the Muslim world?* Thomas Nelson; Strobel, L. (2018). *The case for miracles: A journalist investigates evidence for the supernatural*. Zondervan; Yun, B., & Hattaway, P. (2002). *The heavenly man: The remarkable true story of Chinese Christian brother Yun*. Monarch Books; Tilak, N. V. (2019). *From the Ganges to the Nile: A Hindu’s journey to Christ*. CreateSpace.

reached people but also those unreached by the Gospel to come to know God personally through immediate experience—in Alvin Plantinga’s (1981) terms—such that God becomes a reality at the level of *properly basic beliefs* in their lives⁹⁵. Thus, even if Christian inclusivism *were* true, as I have already indicated, it would not have a universalist scope in any sense—rather, it *would* be a *narrow inclusivism*, “which implies a narrow particularism” (Moreland & Craig, 2017, chapter 34).

Finally, I can summarize my theological-philosophical account as follows:

(1) **God’s sovereignty:** I believe that the Triune Perfect Being, who needed neither anything nor anyone, freely chose—out of His own fullness and according to His good pleasure—to create FMAs who could forever enjoy a blissful, loving relationship with the Perfect Being. By grace, He created FMAs in order to share His love with creatures made in His image and likeness. Among all the PWs the GPB could create, the moment He decides to create a world with FMAs, the range of PWs narrows significantly to those where creatures possess LFW. This would enable them to respond to God in love, thereby enjoying a genuine relationship in which giving and receiving between Creator and creatures would be mutual and continual. However, the GPB does not desire just *any* world with FMAs, for LFW entails the possibility of evil (Sin), and evil is something the GPB abhors, since He is holy. For this reason, the GPB moves from *natural knowledge*⁹⁶ to *middle knowledge*⁹⁷: He knows that, among the remaining PWs, some include Sin, while others do not. It turns out that those PWs where FMAs never Sin are sufficiently deficient as to not be actualized (e.g., such a PW might have only three persons). Therefore, He chooses not to actualize those worlds. What remains are only those PWs in which Sin exists. Thus, on the one hand, it is the loving will of the GPB that a vast number of FMAs dwell with Him forever. On the other hand, the GPB knows that in any PW He might wish to actualize—where a multitude of FMAs are with Him forever—there is Sin.

⁹⁵ I endorse Plantinga’s *Reformed Epistemology*, according to which people can come to know the reality of God’s existence (and even of the truth of several core biblical doctrines) without evidence or argument, on the sole grounds of an immediate experience, after which God (and key biblical doctrines) become properly basic beliefs, like the reality of the past, the existence of the external world, and the reality of other minds apart from one’s own mind (see, e.g., Plantinga, 1981; 1983; 2000; 2015).

⁹⁶ God’s knowledge of all the possibilities, i.e., of everything that *could* happen.

⁹⁷ God’s knowledge of the counterfactuals of creaturely freedom that logically precedes His decree to actualize a specific world (from all the PWs), i.e., the knowledge of what *would* happen *if* certain contingent circumstances *were* true.

(2) **God's love:** The GPB purposes to create a world in which, although there is Sin due to the LFW of FMAs, there is also a great multitude of FMAs who will forever enjoy His love and give Him the love (worship) that corresponds to His dignity. But He knows that, given the reality of Sin in FMAs, attaining such a multitude who will glorify Him forever will come at a high price: He Himself will have to pay for their Sin in order to make it possible for that vast number of FMAs to be with Him eternally (this is required by His holiness and justice).

(3) **God's holiness:** Since the GPB is supremely holy (indeed, He is the standard of morality), He tolerates no deviation from the Good, which is His very character. Thus, He abhors Sin and every sin. Consequently, no Sinner can be with Him (i.e., go to heaven or dwell in His presence). His holiness and purity would immediately cast the Sinner into a state of misery and deprivation—lacking goodness and the generous benefits of His presence.

(4) **God's justice:** Because the GPB is good, He is just—i.e., His goodness obligates Him to give each FMA what they deserve, proportionate to their sin(s). This means that FMAs would have to experience His just judgment forever, undergoing ECT, to satisfy the infinitely grave offense implied by Sin (type 1), due to the GPB's own infinitude.

(5) **God's love (again):** Consequently, in order to save FMAs from His own holy wrath—flowing from His holiness and retributive justice (RJ)—God the Father would have to offer the Person of the Son as a sacrifice. The Son of God would have to assume the nature of FMAs in order to rescue them from the eternal ruin they deserve on account of their Sin. Through substitution, the truly Innocent and Holy One—the incarnate GPB—would have to take the place of FMAs, benefitting any among them who would be willing to receive His benefit. Thus, those FMAs could receive the just forgiveness of the GPB and, through Jesus (the incarnate GPB), go to be with Him forever.

(6) **God's omniscience (again):** Moreover, the GPB knows that certain FMAs whom He might create—whether in this PW or in other similar PWs—are *transworldly damned*, since in all PWs involving LFW and the salvation of great multitudes, these FMAs would freely choose to reject the GPB throughout the time given to them to decide.

(7) **God's sovereignty and providence:** Therefore, all things considered in His omniscience and knowledge of counterfactuals—in His wisdom, He chooses to create the actual world such that there are no FMAs whose earthly lives end (i.e., they die) who, had they heard the good news of the incarnate GPB's sacrifice, would have turned from their Sin to the GPB. The

GPB has arranged the world in such a way that the unevangelized who are not saved are precisely those FMAs who would not have believed, even had they been evangelized.

(8) **God’s mercy:** Thus, a lesser degree of light or revelation given to unevangelized FMAs is a manifestation of the GPB’s mercy, since these individuals will suffer a lesser degree of punishment, having received only general revelation—i.e., the GPB’s self-disclosure in creation and the moral conscience inherent in every FMA made in His image.

(9) **God’s grace:** The GPB, in His great love, does good to all, every day, without self-interest—both to those He has eternally known will turn to Him and to those who will not. His love is universal, impartial, and unconditional. He works in the lives of all FMAs, in all times, to draw them to repentance and trust in His substitutionary and propitiatory Sacrifice against holy wrath toward Sin. He gives sinful FMAs the ability to respond⁹⁸ to Him positively throughout the time He grants them on earth. Even so, some will come out of the prison of trying to construct their identities apart from the GPB, while others will make the One who was sacrificed their greatest treasure.

(10) **God’s justice and love (again):** As a result, some will go to everlasting punishment, and others to everlasting life.

2. **Negatively:** I consider that the three alternative views to the traditionalist one—already discussed in Section III—first, do not represent the teaching of the *Tota Scriptura*, since they present a discordance with other biblical texts that address the same topic; and second, they have problematic philosophical implications that, in my opinion, make them considerably less credible. There are two main problems I see with them: firstly, that—something as clear throughout Scripture as the retributivist character of God’s justice (RJ)—is rejected by ISS; and secondly, that TP and CU—despite their apparent retributivism—fail to recognize that Sin (type 1)—the rejection of God as one’s Lord—involves infinite retribution extended in time *a parte post* inevitably, given the perfectly holy and just character of God (even if, for the sake of argument, sins (type 2)—infractions of God’s moral law—could be paid for by finite suffering in time through punishments “proportional” to the crime).

Nonetheless, I believe each of these views offers valuable insights to enrich my understanding of God and hell:

⁹⁸ I.e., by His *prevenient grace*, by which He convicts individuals of sin, its consequences, and the necessity of turning to God/Christ for forgiveness (See, e.g., John 16:8-10).

From ISS, I retain the idea that hell results from the choice to live separated from God *here and now*. However, hell's punishment is ultimately retributive. Upon arrival, it ceases to be a choice—it *was* a choice but no longer is nor will be, since LFW vanishes there. Hell's purpose is not restoration but retributive punishment for evil committed and chosen in this temporal life.

From TP, I accept that “eternal” may sometimes *refer to the result* (e.g., irreversible destruction). Yet passages like Revelation 14:10–11 prevent me from concluding this eternal result is not also a *permanent process*. Additionally, granting the benefit of the doubt regarding the salvation of children below the age of moral awareness (i.e., before comprehending violations of moral norms), *if* such children are not automatically saved, it is biblically certain they *will not* endure ECT⁹⁹. If hell retributes *personal sins* (as I firmly hold), infants—lacking personal sins—cannot be punished. Thus, *if* they are ultimately not saved through Christ's sacrifice and incorporated among the redeemed, the only alternative would be their *immediate annihilation* (not a TP, since there is nothing to be punished due to their moral innocence). Yet extra-biblical evidence¹⁰⁰—such as near-death experiences—suggests that infants (even the unborn) may be in heaven. If that is the case, infants' annihilation hypothesis would not apply.

From CU, I affirm that God's *heart* indeed desires universal salvation. However, due to LFW, this desire appears eternally frustrated. No FW seems to exist where universal salvation (or eternal sinless communion with God) coexists with LFW—a necessary condition for genuine love.

⁹⁹ Personally, I reject the version of the doctrine of *Original Sin* according to which Adam's sin is automatically imputed to his progeny, as such a belief lacks clear biblical support. According to Romans 5:12, “Sin came into the world through one man, and death through sin, and so death spread to all men because all sinned” (*ESV*, 2016). Thus, either spiritual death (or a fallen nature) is passed on to all humans *because* of Adam's sin, by virtue of their descent from him; or spiritual death occurs in the life of each individual *after* they come to *sin* personally, as they learn to distinguish good from evil (cf. Isaiah 7:15–16).

¹⁰⁰ Colton, then nearly four-year-old boy, had a near-death experience later documented in the book (and subsequent film) *Heaven is for Real* (Burpo & Vincent, 2010). The account describes how his father Todd—an evangelical pastor—was preparing a sermon one evening when Colton suddenly told his mother Sonja he had “two sisters,” referencing their 1998 miscarriage. When his shocked mother asked how he knew about the lost baby, Colton explained that the child herself had told him she died in his mother's womb, adding that God had “adopted” her. Colton added that his sister resembled his living sibling Cassie but was smaller with dark hair. He also noted they had never given her a name (chapter 17). In a separate revelation, Colton told his father about meeting his great-grandfather “Pop,” who had died in an accident three decades earlier (chapter 16).

B. My Rationale

All in all, I believe that ECT constitutes *the only* form of punishment for Sinners that coheres with the nature of the GPB. In section II.B.2 (pp. 24-27), I argued that the existence of a GPB *entails* an ECT punishment in any PW where, at least, two conditions are met:

- (a) FMAs exist
- (b) At least one FMA has Sinned

There I presented a detailed rationale to demonstrate the *compatibility* and *necessary interconnection* between PBT and ECT, where I outlined God's solution to the apparent love-justice dilemma. Below, I formalize that argument:

P1. The Greatest Possible Being (GPB) is a Being Worthy of Worship (BWW), and as such, He possesses all great-making properties, including qualitative infinity (QI) and moral goodness, which encompasses perfect holiness, love, and justice.

P2. All Free Moral Agents (FMAs) were created to have a blissful love relationship with the GPB and they morally owe Him the worship He deserves in virtue of His ontological perfection—worship expressed through wholehearted love for Him and demonstrated through perfect obedience to His commands as the natural result of that love.

P3. Sin (type 1) is FMA's rejection of the GPB as Lord of their lives—a moral offense of infinite gravity due to the QI and morally perfect nature of the One offended.

P4. Because the GPB is perfectly just and holy, He must rectify every moral disorder caused by FMAs¹⁰¹. That is, any injustice must be justly addressed; the GPB cannot ignore it or leave it unpaid.

P5. A Sin of infinite gravity (against the QI GPB) requires satisfaction of equal QI value to restore moral order.

P6. Finite and Sinful FMAs, being limited in nature and morally imperfect due to Sin, are metaphysically incapable of rendering QI satisfaction to the GPB.

SC1. Therefore, FMAs who Sin incur an infinite moral debt they cannot repay.

¹⁰¹ A very original and relevant contribution to the defense of ECT—one that does not rely on the notion that sinning against an infinite being necessitates infinite punishment, though still drawing on the ideas of Anselm of Canterbury—has been offered by Haratine and Smith (2023).

P7. If FMAs were annihilated, their infinite offense would remain everlastingly unpaid, leaving a permanent moral disorder in God's universe.

P8. But such an outcome is logically and metaphysically incompatible with the nature of the GPB, who cannot allow everlasting injustice to exist unresolved (unpunished).

SC2. Therefore, annihilationism is logically and metaphysically impossible in any possible world (PW) in which the GPB exists¹⁰².

C1. Hence, since Sinner FMAs are metaphysically incapable of rendering QI satisfaction to the GPB, they must continue to exist and endure the just retributive consequences of their Sin forever—i.e., ECT is necessary to uphold God's perfect justice.

P9. The GPB, being also perfectly loving, wills to save FMAs from the just (ECT) consequences of their Sin, by restoring them to a right relationship with Himself.

P10. No act of obedience or good works by FMAs can provide satisfaction, since these are already morally owed to God by nature and therefore do not exceed FMAs' duty.

P11. Only the GPB can render a satisfaction of QI value—but only FMAs are liable for the debt.

SC3. Therefore, only someone who is both truly divine (i.e., the QI GPB) and who truly partakes in the nature of the FMAs He intends to save can satisfy the QI kind of debt on behalf of Sinful FMAs, acting as their legal proxy.

P12. If the Gospel message is true, in the Incarnation, the GPB became human in the person of Jesus Christ, offering His QI life as a legal proxy to satisfy divine justice on behalf of FMAs.

P13. This satisfaction makes it possible for FMAs, through repentance and faith in Christ, to escape the everlasting retributive consequences of Sin (ECT), and be reconciled to the GPB.

C2. Therefore, ECT is the necessary and just consequence of Sin against the GPB that sinful FMAs must endure—unless¹⁰³ they accept the legal pardon offered and accomplished on their behalf through repentance and faith in Christ, the incarnate GPB, the only one capable of rendering satisfaction for a QI offense¹⁰⁴.

¹⁰² That is, the GPB, as the most perfect being, possesses ontologically the attribute of necessary existence, which entails that He exists in all PWs.

¹⁰³ Unless they accept the legal pardon accomplished on their behalf by the GPB in incarnate form.

¹⁰⁴ It is important to note what Peterson (in E. Fudge & Peterson, 2000) has pointed out regarding Christ's hellish suffering on our behalf:

The traditional understanding of the punishment of hell includes two elements: separation from God (*poena damni*, the punishment of the damned) and the positive infliction of torments in body and soul (*poena sensus*,

C. My Concerns

As I have already stated in outlining my *spiritual* motivation for writing this paper (see p. 6), the way humans think of God and hell will *influence* both their personal and collective behavior and attitudes toward:

1. Proclamation: How believers—and the Church in general—proclaim the Gospel to nonbelievers (i.e., how passionately, conscientiously¹⁰⁵, urgently, and with what kind of exhortations they do so)¹⁰⁶(see 2 Corinthians 5:11; Jude 23).

2. Sanctification: The seriousness with which Christians pursue sanctification (e.g., how promptly they obey God’s Word whenever they find that it exhorts them to change in specific areas) (see Romans 6; Colossians 3:5ff).

3. Worship: The way believers worship God, in view of their perception of His attributes or character (depending on how they conceive of divine justice and mercy and their interrelation, their worship may be shaped by whether they see God primarily as a “righteous Judge” or a “compassionate Savior”), since belief in ECT might foster a sense of sober reverence (see Revelation 14:7).

4. Moral choices of nonbelievers: The way nonbelievers who are familiar with Christian ideas behave in this life—what they allow themselves to do, and to what extent (e.g., assumptions about ultimate annihilation or postmortem sanctification could lead them to believe that “it is not a big deal” if they sin “a little more” while they live—or even that suicide could be a viable escape from life’s difficulties, since after a finite period of punishment they might simply be no more or

the punishment of sense). Jesus suffered the punishment of hell for sinners. That he endured separation from the Father’s love is evidenced by his cry, “My God, my God, why have you forsaken me?” (Mt 27:46). On Calvary’s cross Jesus also endured God’s wrath. In Gethsemane Jesus was deeply grieved at the prospect of drinking the cup of God’s wrath (Jer 25:15). This is why he thrice asked the Father, “If it is possible, may this cup be taken from me” (Mt 26:39; compare Mt 26:42, 44). On the cross, then, the Son of God suffered the pains of hell: separation from God and the positive infliction of torments in body and soul. (chapter 9)

¹⁰⁵ Robert Peterson (in Gregg, 2024, chapter 10) raises this same concern in relation to the potential consequence of the spread of the TP view of hell.

¹⁰⁶ I agree with Gregg’s (2024, chapter 10) observation that the ultimate motivation for evangelism should not be fear of what will happen to people in eternity, but rather the glory of God. However, I believe he somewhat oversimplifies the traditionalist perspective in this regard. The traditionalist seeks to live and evangelize for the glory of God in Christ, yet also finds a serious additional incentive in the doctrine of ECT. These two motivations can, and often do, coexist: the pursuit of God’s glory aligns with the greatest commandment, while the desire to prevent others from experiencing eternal conscious torment serves as a secondary—but weighty—motivation rooted in the second greatest commandment, love for one’s neighbor.

eventually enter heaven, as they, in their sin-distorted vision, wish it would be (see Proverbs 14:12).

Considering the above, my Christian concern or fear is that, if any of the alternative views were to become the “official” or mainstream position within Christian churches, yet *it turned out that* ECT is true (as I believe and have contended throughout this paper), then teaching such doctrines would amount to:

1) A betrayal of the trust Jesus placed in the Church, whose function is to be the “pillar and buttress of the truth” (1 Timothy 3:15) in a world of lies and of truth manipulated to suit the hearer.

2) A failure to believe Christ’s repeated warnings about a coming punishment that is everlasting, horrific, conscious, mental and physical, and that entails irreversible separation from God, from His people, and from His joy.

3) A great favor to the “father of lies,” (John 8:44) who seeks to “deceive the whole world” (Revelation 12:9) by any means, so long as people do not turn to the Gospel of the Lord Jesus Christ (2 Corinthians 4:4). For these doctrines could lead nonbelievers into self-deception, allowing them to continue in their sins under the false illusion that their punishment will one day come to an end—and perhaps even that they will enjoy heaven, where their Creator dwells, whom—for now—they persist in ignoring as if nothing happened, expecting eschatological mercy and compassion, when in truth, “because of [their] hard and impenitent heart” they are only storing up “wrath for [themselves] on the day of wrath when God’s righteous judgment will be revealed” (Romans 2:5, *ESV*, 2016).

Here I do not seek to sound polemical or to discredit alternative views, but simply to highlight the potential spiritual consequences that widespread acceptance of these competing views of hell *could* entail on both a medium and large scale—*assuming* that ECT is true. As I argued above (p. 6), although an error in biblical interpretation does not, by itself, *determine*¹⁰⁷ how a person will live, it can nevertheless *serve as* an additional instrument of deception.

¹⁰⁷ I believe, however, that the accusation—reported by Gregg (2024, chapter 12)—often made by traditionalists against Universalism and Conditionalism, namely, that these views render evangelism and mission unnecessary, is ultimately misleading. Neither position *necessarily* entails such a practical consequence. E.g., there are notable proponents of alternative views to ECT, such as theologian and evangelist Michael Green, who, despite his TP position, remained fully committed to missionary work.

D. My Hope

1. Theologically: The Kingdom of Heaven

It is my theological, Scripture-based conviction that we human beings were created for a blissful, personal love relationship with God—the only BWW. Thus, “God wants us to know Him, glorify Him, and enjoy Him forever¹⁰⁸.” However, we broke that relationship through Sin—a willful rejection of God as our absolute Lord—and, as a consequence, we now “wander aimlessly, lost in this world” due to that alienation (Gamgebeli-Doroshenko, 2022).

But the Good News of the Gospel is that “God came in the Person of Jesus Christ ‘to seek and to save that which was lost’ (Lk. 19:10)” — “He came to reconcile us to Himself through the death of His Son Jesus Christ (God incarnate), our perfect human representative, who on the cross suffered the penalty for our rebellion against God, His purpose, and His commandments” (Gamgebeli-Doroshenko, 2022).

After three days, Jesus rose from the dead and appeared alive to many witnesses, thereby confirming that He was who He claimed to be during His earthly ministry (Acts 17:31). Since Jesus had no personal sin, He did not deserve to experience death (1 Peter 3:18). Consequently, it would have been unjust for Him to remain in that state (Acts 2:24). Therefore, God raised Him from the dead and taught us that “everyone who believes in him receives forgiveness of sins through his name” (Acts 10:43, *ESV*, 2016).

I believe that all this was done, by His grace (Ephesians 2:1–10), in order to:

restore and return us to the relationship that we were created for and so that we would enjoy that abundant and true Life that He intended for us in the Kingdom that God inaugurated, that He is now extending and that He will fully establish on earth when He comes in glory for the second time. (Gamgebeli-Doroshenko, 2022)

At the second coming, “Christ will judge the world with justice and the renewed/recreated earth will become the Kingdom of God forever. God will be King, and those redeemed by Christ will be His beloved people” (Gamgebeli-Doroshenko, 2022).

¹⁰⁸ Allusion to Question 1 of *The Westminster Shorter Catechism* (1647).

It is my hope that, from that day on, “we will marvel at who and what He is like, we will live glorifying Him and to glorify Him, and we will enjoy Him forever” (Gamagebeli-Doroshenko, 2022).

Therefore, although I affirm the reality of hell—conceived as ECT—for all who resist God as King and Lord of their lives, I also believe that the destiny of all who trust in Christ Jesus will be everlasting joy in the very presence of the Triune God. I hold that humankind was created for communion with God, and that outside of a relationship with Yahweh, through Jesus the Messiah, humanity wanders aimlessly—empty and unfulfilled—throughout life. Human beings were made by God and for God, and apart from that relationship, they live in contradiction to the original purpose for which they were created.

Lamentably, if they continue resisting God’s grace and kindness—which each day seeks to lead them to repentance (Romans 2:4)—they will, at the moment of death, have *sealed* their everlasting fate (Hebrews 9:27). After Jesus’ second coming, the ungodly will be eternally “‘shut out from the presence of the Lord and from the glory of his might’ (2 Thess. 1:9), while believers will inherit eternal life and immortality through the gospel, attaining the purpose [they] were created for” (Gamagebeli-Doroshenko, 2022).

2. Philosophically: Optimally Balanced World

It is my hope, and my PBT-based philosophical-theological conviction, that among all the PWs God could have created, He, in His perfect goodness and love, actualized a world that has “an optimal balance between the number of the saved and the number of the damned” (Craig, 1989, p. 185):

Given the truth of certain counterfactuals of creaturely freedom, it was not feasible for God to actualize a world having as many saved as but with no more damned than the actual world. The happiness of the saved should not be precluded by the admittedly tragic circumstance that their salvation has as its concomitant the damnation of many others, for the fate of the damned is the result of their own free choice. (Craig, 1989, p. 185)

God, in His sovereignty, could have actualized any PW; but since He desires to create worlds in which FMAs possess the LFW-good that enables them to genuinely love—so that they can be His moral reflection—God employs His middle knowledge to choose and actualize one of those PWs where there is an optimal balance between the freely saved and the unsaved FMAs, such that the unsaved would not have been saved in any other PW, given their transworld damnation.

Directly actualizing the heavenly state—where the greatest number of people could freely enjoy God and glorify Him forever without any damnation whatsoever—appears to be an unviable option within a libertarian framework. As Craig replied to Bradley in their debate, “heaven isn’t a possible world. A PW “is a maximal state of affairs--which includes not just the afterlife, but the pre-life on the way to heaven. And the point is here that ... it may not be feasible for God to actualize heaven in isolation from such an antecedent world” (Craig & Bradley, 1994). Craig explains:

Heaven may not be a possible world when you take it in isolation by itself. It may be that the only way in which God could actualize a heaven of free creatures all worshipping Him and not falling into sin would be by having, so to speak, this run-up to it, this advance life during which there is a veil of decision-making in which some people choose for God and some people against God. Otherwise you don’t know that heaven is an actualizable world. You have no way of knowing that possibility. (Craig & Bradley, 1994)

Thus, if GPB exists, plausibly, there are no FWs that would combine both (a) universal salvation (or universal Sinless state) and (b) a vast number of FMAs who never Sin. Consequently, God, in His perfect wisdom and goodness, prefers to actualize a world in which, although universal salvation does not obtain, (1) a vast multitude is freely saved, and (2) all those who are ultimately damned are so by their own LFW—even possibly exhibiting transworld damnation across all FWs in which they could exist.

In conclusion, to address what might be termed the *soteriological problem of evil*—i.e., the apparent inconsistency between (P1) “God is omniscient, omnipotent, and omnibenevolent” and (P2) “Some persons do not receive Christ and are damned” (Craig, 1989, p. 180)—I affirm, along

with Craig, the following proposition: “God has actualized a world containing an optimal balance between saved and unsaved, and those who are unsaved suffer from transworld damnation” (p. 184). Therefore, it is my hope and conviction that the actual world is indeed that optimally balanced world.

VI. Conclusions

This Master’s Thesis has pursued a comprehensive exploration of the compatibility between PBT and the doctrine of ECT. (I) I began by introducing the topic and defining key terms for the reader’s sake; (II) I then discussed the concepts of God and hell from both theological and philosophical perspectives and provided an argument for ECT given PBT; (III) I analyzed the strengths and weaknesses of the four major views of hell, contending that ECT surpasses the others—both theologically and, especially for this work, philosophically; (IV) I addressed and refuted a wide range of objections to ECT—spanning theological, logical, and moral domains; and (V) I concluded by demonstrating the rationale behind my belief in the actual compatibility between PBT and ECT.

So, are PBT and ECT compatible after all? Although ECT may *prima facie* appear to be a deeply objectionable doctrine under PBT, *ultima facie* it seems not only compatible but even metaphysically unavoidable:

Necessarily, if a GPB exists, then in all PW, if there exists an FMA who has Sinned, then ECT obtains.

Formally: $\Box[\text{GPB} \rightarrow \forall \text{PW}((\exists x(\text{FMA}(x) \wedge \text{Sinned}(x))) \rightarrow \text{ECT})]$

By analyzing this significant theological and philosophical topic, I have sought to defend the internal coherence of traditional Judeo-Christian theism within the framework of contemporary debates in analytic philosophy of religion. My hope is that this contribution enables readers to recognize both the reasonableness of belief in the biblical God and to identify Him as the GPB. If so, one may confidently affirm that the biblical God is indeed a Being Worthy of Worship (BWW).

Since the present discussion has been conducted on theoretical grounds, I would like to conclude by offering a pastoral word to the reader through this thoughtful reflection by William Lane Craig:

I hope that no reader has been offended by what might appear to be a rather dry and dispassionate discussion of the salvation and damnation of people apart from Christ. But with such an emotionally explosive issue on the table, it seems to me that it is prudent to treat it with reserve. No orthodox Christian *likes* the doctrine of hell or delights in anyone's condemnation. I truly wish that universalism were true, but it is not. My compassion toward those in other world religions is therefore expressed, not in pretending that they are not lost and dying without Christ, but by my supporting and making every effort myself to communicate to them the life-giving message of salvation through Christ. (Craig, 1989, pp. 186-187)

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